

HΣPHÆSTUS

Heritage in EuroPe: new tecHnologies in crAft for
prEServing and innovaTing fUtureS

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Report for researchers on the methodology of mapping craft values and analyzing craft controversies

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Abstract	This report presents an original craft mapping methodology that combines ethnographic methods, historical approaches and design-mapping methods to examine the values of craft in an ecosystem. The report also presents the research results from the craft mapping methodology of HEPHAESTUS which has been used in each of the four European craft ecosystems in focus and across them. This methodology has allowed the project: to observe their socio-economic and cultural infrastructures; to capture their historical and contemporary identities; to untangle the current urgencies of the members of the ecosystems and their degree of resistance and acceptance towards cutting-edge technologies and sustainability and to map their values. By unpacking sustainability and digitalisation as key controversies, the report highlights how heritage crafts both face risks and generate new pathways for renewal.
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Deliverable Lead	University of Gothenburg (UGOT)
Author(s)	Elena Raviola (UGOT), Ulises Navarro Aguiar (UGOT), Enrico Macciò (CBS), Manfredi de Bernard (Ca' Foscari), Maria Lusiani (Ca' Foscari)
Point of contact	Elena.raviola@gu.se
Reviewers & contributors	Marta Gasparin, Marius Gudman- Høyer, Lea Jacobsen (CBS)

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Executive Summary

This report presents the results of Task 1.1 of the HEPHAESTUS project, which investigated the social, cultural, and historical development of different European craft ecosystems, namely Venice, Bassano del Grappa, Bornholm, and Dals Långed. The research examined how craft heritage and contemporary practices are being reshaped by the urgent challenges of technology, sustainability, and livelihood.

The study developed a methodology that combined ethnographic, historical, and design-mapping approaches. Ethnographic fieldwork, including participant observation and interviews with craftmakers, policymakers, and other stakeholders, was complemented by autoethnographic diaries in which makers experimenting with new technologies documented their reflections. Visual ethnography and artistic experimentation, such as motion capture and material exploration, were used to foreground embodied knowledge and aesthetic experience. Historical research traced the evolution of materials, processes, and socio-economic structures through archival sources, situating current practices within longer trajectories of continuity and change. Finally, design-based mapping methods, including participatory workshops and controversy mapping, provided ways to visualize tensions around sustainability and digitization and to co-create reflective tools with practitioners and communities.

The findings show that across all ecosystems, craft is deeply embedded in local identities and cultural continuity, while also being exposed to pressures from globalisation, market precarity, and policy neglect. In Italy, issues of competition, institutional recognition, and gentrification frame contemporary debates. On Bornholm, craft is tightly interwoven with sustainability initiatives, from circular economy practices to material recycling, though makers face structural challenges to sustaining livelihoods. In Sweden, experimental projects such as Open Wood and digital residencies at FabLab Venice highlight both the opportunities and controversies of integrating new technologies into craft ecosystems, showing that digital tools can enrich practice without displacing embodied knowledge, provided appropriate infrastructures and support are in place. Across sites, livelihood emerges as a persistent challenge, with many craftmakers navigating patchwork careers, multiple income streams, and reliance on institutional or community support.

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1. Introduction

This report, based on task 1.1, delivers the results of a 2.5 years long research process within work package 1 of HEPHAESTUS. In the spirit of the project, this research process has significantly benefitted from intersections with other work packages and from earlier deliverables within the same work package. This task in the work package, which has laid throughout the project the scientific ground for many other tasks, has involved researchers from UGOT, CBS and Ca' Foscari in a collaborative and continuous process both to develop the robust methodology presented here and to conduct the research work whose results are presented here.

Craft heritage has been recognised at the policy level as central to Europe's cultural identity and future. The European Commission's *Framework for Action on Cultural Heritage (2018)* and the *New European Bauhaus* initiative emphasise the role of traditional practices in fostering sustainability, inclusion, and innovation. As scholarship has shown, craft practices form a key part of Europe's intangible cultural heritage and play a crucial role in sustaining cultural identity, community cohesion, and local economies (UNESCO, 2003; Bortolotto, 2007; Niedderer et al., 2014). However, across Europe craft heritage faces mounting pressures from demographic change, economic restructuring, and cultural globalisation, while also being reshaped by sustainability transitions and the spread of digital technologies. Conventional approaches to documenting craft heritage often fail to capture the shifting urgencies experienced by practitioners and stakeholders. UNESCO's framework for identifying crafts at risk, which is grounded in the UNESCO's *Convention for Safeguarding Intangible Cultural Heritage (2003)* and visualize it in an innovative and interactive tool, highlights a wide range of threats—including negative attitudes, demographic decline, de-contextualisation, environmental degradation, and economic pressures. This underscores the need for new tools of analysis.

To address the challenge of European craft heritage today, HEPHAESTUS develops a methodology that combines historical methods and contemporary ethnography with controversy mapping. Applied across four craft ecosystems—Venice, Bassano del Grappa, Bornholm, and Dals Långed—this approach makes it possible to trace transformations in materials and practices in their socio-economic and cultural embeddedness, identify contested values, and visualise how debates around sustainability and digitalisation unfold within specific local contexts. In recognizing the role of craft as an intangible cultural heritage to foster cultural diversity (in a globalized society and economy) and sustainable development, HEPHAESTUS shifts the focus to European local communities (besides the UNESCO's framework, which has mostly focused on indigenous communities) and recognizes the varieties of our many Europes.

The embeddedness of craft work that we unpack in this report is in line with the spirit and framework of the UNESCO's classification of risks to intangible cultural heritage, which identify nine elements of risk, i.e. negative attitudes, demographic issues, decontextualisation, environmental degradation, weakened practice and transmission, cultural globalisation, new products and techniques, loss of objects/systems, economic

pressure. Considering the “deep-seated interdependence between the intangible cultural heritage and the tangible cultural and natural heritage” (UNESCO Convention for Safeguarding Intangible Cultural Heritage, 2003), HEPHAESTUS unpacks this interdependence and in a certain way extends it to the social, economic and cultural conditions of possibility of craft work over time.

This report is focused on two outputs of the task 1.1: firstly, the development of a robust and creative methodology for mapping the social, cultural and historical development of craft; secondly, the results of the analysis of the controversies emerging from the mapping as case studies to understand the social, cultural and historical development of craft in novel ways. The overall objective of this report is to offer researchers and other stakeholders, like policy makers, craftmakers and interest organizations, a general methodology to explore and discuss the value of craft in new ways that combine an historical understanding to contemporary relevance of crafts. Ultimately, as the report shows, the methodological combination developed in HEPHAESTUS allows to observe craft ecosystems’ socio-economic and cultural infrastructures, to capture the current urgencies of craft ecosystems, to understand their degree of resistance or acceptance of digital and cutting-edge technologies and sustainability actions as well as to capture historical and contemporary identity and map craft values.

The report is structured in two main sections: Craft Mapping Methodology and Craft Mapping Results.

2. Craft Mapping Methodology

The development of a robust and creative methodology for mapping the social, cultural and historical development of craft synthesizes the methodological endeavors of HEPHAESTUS as an international team of researchers and practitioners of craft in a strong and growing collaboration. These endeavors are grounded not only in interdisciplinarity, but also in transdisciplinarity, as this is an effort to both integrate academic disciplines and to move across academic knowledge and practitioners’ involvement in research (Vienni-Baptista et al., 2022). In this spirit, this methodology functions as a way of collaborating among researchers from different disciplines and performing transdisciplinary knowledge production, crossing institutional and professional boundaries, as a reflective approach to collecting and analyzing data on our craft ecosystems, and as a way to co-create with practitioners a third space where up-to-date relevant knowledge can be created at the benefit of academia, practice and policy makers (Palmer et al., 2025).

The ultimate aims of the craft mapping methodology are: to observe craft ecosystems’ socio-economic and cultural infrastructures in the making; to capture the current urgencies of craft ecosystems, as voiced by the members of the ecosystem and especially in relation to sustainability and digitalization; to understand the degree of resistance or acceptance of digital and cutting edge technologies and sustainability actions by the members of the ecosystems; to allow local policymakers to make better-informed and more-reflexive decisions which are grounded in the ecosystems’ shared historical and contemporary

identity; to map and communicate values of craft. The results of the application of the craft mapping methodology to our four ecosystems in HEPHAESTUS, according to these aims, will be presented in the next section, while this section is dedicated to delineate the methodological building blocks we have developed. Although not the primary goal of this report, we also see this methodology as potentially relevant and generalizable for the study of other cultural and creative sectors, especially to understand them as embedded in places.

2.1. A processual note on the development of the methodology

This methodology was developed over the course of the project by means of regular meetings between researchers across ecosystems, regular meetings between researchers and practitioners (craftmakers and policymakers) in each ecosystem and yearly consortium-wide meetings with the active presence and voice of our community of craft ambassadors. Particularly important for the scientific grounding of this methodology have been the reading seminars, in which we have developed a simple research practice of reading and discussing which makes HEPHAESTUS uniquely cohesive and relevant for practice and policy makers across the specificities of the ecosystems with whom we have worked. In this reading seminars, researchers have gathered across their disciplines around seminal texts and other materials, which we have read and analyzed carefully. We have engaged in research literature from craft studies, organization studies, science and technology studies, sociology, anthropology, and history (e.g., Dioun et al., 2025; von Busch, 2022; Paxson, 2010, 2008; Sabel & Zeitlin, 1985; Wadhvani & Lubinski, 2017; Epstein, 2008; Luckman & Thomas, 2023). This regular practice of the reading seminar has turned the texts into boundary objects (Star & Griesemer, 1989) which have triggered discussions with relevance for and direct reference to the different contexts of the ecosystems.

Working around texts as boundary objects, our seminars fill different functions: **i)** they represent also collective interpretive situations guiding our following fieldwork and analysis; **ii)** they solicit comparisons and understanding of variations of craft across ecosystems; and **iii)** they strengthen integration in our collective research group.

The main unit of investigation in HEPHAESTUS has been the ecosystem in which single crafts are embedded through relationship across craft specialties and other societal sectors rather than in isolation. It is, thus, important for our readers - researchers and policy-makers alike – that the methodology outlined here is directed at encompassing the relationality of crafts and craftmakers' work rather than their specificities. This is an important boundary condition in light of the ultimate goal of this methodology, namely to articulate the social, cultural and historical development of craft.

2.2. Three methodological pillars

Our methodology is based on three main pillars: (a) ethnographic methods; (b) historical research; (c) design mapping methods. In this report, we attend to each of these pillars by describing how we have used them and summarizing our key recommendations for their

role and deployment in mapping the social, cultural and historical development of craft in different ecosystems.

2.2.1. Ethnographic methods

Ethnography is a qualitative methodological approach that is widely used in social sciences (Pink, 2013) and increasingly in humanities and the arts as well (Foster, 1985). Originally the methodological toolset of anthropology, it has over the last 40 years expanded from the study of far-away tribes to the study of phenomena and places which are nearby and in contexts that are familiar for the researcher. Becoming ethnographers in European craft ecosystems encourages the perspective of a plural Europe, where variation, differences and local histories make visible and tangible many Europes rather than a homogeneous story of craft, while at the same time offering the granularity for a synthesis of the themes of the controversies around craft across the different ecosystems.

Through the use of what is called “fieldwork”, requiring the researcher’s immersion in a field, ethnographic methods aim primarily at to generating a situated understanding of practices and meanings as they unfold and are constructed in the field. Ethnography is, thus, grounded in the close engagement of the researcher with the social world under study, combining sustained presence, observation, and interaction (Hammersley & Atkinson, 2019; Emerson, Fretz, & Shaw, 2011). Our ethnographic approaches find themselves in recent lines of development of ethnographic research, intersecting team ethnographies with the tradition of urban ethnography (Jackson, 1985), visual anthropology (Pink, 2006) and praxiography (Czarniawska, 2017).

The combination of insights and skills required for different kinds of ethnographic work – encompassing for instance both interviewing and filming – and the ambition to examine different places pose some challenges to the classical idea of the lone ethnographer that spends years in the field. The collaboration in a team also requires and gives access to a wide range of skills. It is of utmost importance for our methodology to balance immersion in local ecosystems, rather than fragmenting interviews among many researchers, with the transfer of knowledge and regular exchange within our international network across ecosystems, as well as the integration of specific skills such as the production of visual anthropological material.

Ethnographic data collection

In order to collect data, we have primarily relied on three methods: interviews, observations and photography/filming.

Ethnographic interviews provided access to participants’ own accounts of their experiences, motivations, and perspectives, while observations allowed attention to routines, interactions, and material arrangements that may not be verbalized (Spradley, 1980; Pink, 2015). The combination of interviews and observations is a core strength of ethnographic research, as it enables the researcher to capture both how actors narrate their practices and how these practices are performed in context (Clifford & Marcus, 1986; Schatz, 2009). Taken together,

these methods allow for a more comprehensive and interpretive account of craft as embedded in the local systems of relations rather than in isolation.

For the interviews, based on the extensive experience of interviewing in our team (e.g. Raviola, 2010, 2022; Gasparin & Neyland, 2022; Lusiani & Langley, 2019; Navarro Aguiar, 2017, 2020) and on the sharing discussions during the reading seminars (see above), we developed a shared interview guide that encompassed the interests and themes that we wanted to focus on and we expected to provoke conversations. The guide, which is attached in the appendix to this report, was intended both as an instrument of sharing in the research group and as flexible enough to be adapted to the local specificities and conversations.

In using these guides, it is of outmost important to remain informed by ethnographic sensitivity to the field and the participants we encounter. The guide, thus, shapes the interviews to be a combination between ethnographic conversations and semi-structured interviews, by either performing several interviews with the same people and thus allowing for different modes of interaction or leaving space for both broad conversations and more structured questioning in the rythm of one long interview. The mode of meaning-making of ethnographic interviews is open-ended and dialogical, often resembling a guided conversation rather than a rigidly structured exchange (Spradley, 1979; Heyl, 2001). This format allows participants to introduce themes they find meaningful, while also giving the researcher opportunities to probe how practices and interpretations are embedded in everyday life (Kvale, 2009). The aim is not only to gather information, but to situate narratives within the broader social and material contexts in which they are produced (Hammersley & Atkinson, 2019). In practicing our interview guide, we used ethnographic interviews (Hammersley & Atkinson, 2019; Heyl, 2001), leaving the interviewees large space for narrating as if in their own social context.

By treating interviews as co-constructed accounts, rather than transparent windows into reality, ethnographic researchers remain attentive to how knowledge emerges through interaction between interviewer and participant (Holstein & Gubrium, 1995). This is part of our methodology and it is very important for HEPHAESTUS researchers to apply this interview guide in the different ecosystems so that local and sustainable relationships are established between the craft communities and researchers in an efficient and effective way.

Observations were conducted in three main ways with different rationalities: First, we observed craftmakers in their workshops; second, we observed moments of collective actions; third, we gathered auto-ethnographic material from a selected number of craftmakers in their experimentations with new technologies. Workshop visits allowed for close attention to the embodied, material, and relational aspects of craft practice, including how tools, techniques, and tacit knowledge are enacted in situ (Ingold, 2013; Pink, 2015). The figures below portray some of the workshops we visited, as a way to signal the material intensity of these workshops and at the same time their diversity.

Figure 1 – Ceramic workshops in Bassano del Grappa, Italy.

Figure 2 – Blacksmith shared workshop in Fengersfors, Sweden, at Not Quite

Figure 3 – Glass workshops in Bornholm

Craft events such as fairs and festivals function as field-configuring events (Lampel & Meyer, 2008; Schüßler, Rüling, & Wittneben, 2014) and can often represent important moments where the values of craft are articulated and possibly debated. Observing festivals and fairs thus provided opportunities to study how crafts are displayed, exchanged, and celebrated in more performative and organizationally dense contexts, where professional identities and market relationships are negotiated (Moeran & Strandgaard Pedersen, 2011). We have also participated at different fairs and events on craft, like the Craft Days in West Sweden, the Ceramics Fairs in Nove and Faenza, the Artistic Craft Week in Venice and others. When doing fieldwork, most interviews have been conducted in the craftspeople workshops, thus allowing us to observe the spatiality and materiality of craftwork. We have also interviewed local policy makers in their working space.

Figure 4 - Ceramic festival in Nove

Figure 5 – Craft Cirkus at the *Craft Days* in Dals Långed

Figure 6 – *European Craft Contest 2004* in Bornholm

Apart from researchers' observations of craft work and collective action events, it is also fruitful to engage the practitioners in auto-ethnographies in order to create their own spaces of reflections and account for their own voices. Autoethnography, in fact, offers a valuable lens for understanding the embodied and experiential dimensions of craft in relation to new technologies. By asking craftmakers to document their reflections in diaries during experimental processes involving new technologies, the project situates them not only as practitioners but also as narrators of their own encounters with digital tools, which have been developed in collaboration with WP2 and, in particular, the FabLab Venice. This method allows the subtleties of material engagement, hesitation, and discovery to emerge in ways that conventional observation often overlooks. The diaries capture how makers articulate tensions between tacit, embodied knowledge and the demands of technological systems, while also revealing moments of play, resistance, or appropriation. In this way, autoethnography becomes a tool for preserving experiential knowledge, foregrounding the voices of makers themselves, and situating technological experimentation within the lived realities of craft practice. As Ellis, Adams and Bochner (2011) argue, autoethnography not only connects personal experience with cultural meaning, but also creates space for reflexivity and critique. In design and craft research, similar approaches have been employed to illuminate the intimate, situated nature of making and to highlight the interplay of materials, tools, and identity (e.g. Cunliffe, 2016; Mäkelä, 2007). See figures below for examples of auto-ethnographic diaries

Figure 7 – Extracts from autoethnographic journals from craft-tech residencies.

Finally, as a third form of observation – researchers' observations recorded in fieldnotes and craftmakers' auto-ethnographic journals – we also engaged elements of visual ethnography, especially by collaborating with work package 3 and using art-based methods. Visual ethnography provides a method to document and analyse craft practices through images, videos, and other visual media, capturing aspects of making that are often invisible in textual accounts (Pink, 2013; Banks & Zeitlyn, 2015). By focusing on the gestures, materials, and spatial arrangements involved in craft, visual methods reveal both the processes and the aesthetic qualities of work in situ as well as it can be used as a sensory process to trigger discussions and debates with practitioners and policy-makers. In collaborating with the artists' duo D20 both in their initial work *Atmospheres of Craft* and their subsequent work with self-taped stories of speculative objects of craft, these visual and artistic outputs allow us researchers to access the embodied, temporal, and expressive dimensions of craft, highlighting the interplay between material engagement, creativity, and cultural meaning (Ingold, 2013; Mäkelä, 2007). Ethnographic observation, in fact, in both everyday and not-so-everyday settings involves not only recording visible practices but also attending to sensory atmospheres, rhythms, and interactions that might remain unspoken in interviews (Emerson, Fretz, & Shaw, 2011). This combination enabled a layered understanding of craft as both a situated practice and a field with a complex articulation and intersection of values.

Table 1 details the empirical material we have collected, including interviews in each ecosystems and different kinds of observations.

TABLE 1 - EMPIRICAL MATERIAL FROM ETHNOGRAPHIC METHODS

Interviews			
<i>Dals Långed and Fengersfors</i>			
Social group	Nr. of interviews	Nr. of interviewees	Audiorecorded
Craftmakers	26	13	20
Policy makers	4	4	4
Schools/educators	8	6	8
Local organizations	10	10	6
Local residents	5	5	3
	53	38	41
<i>Bornholm</i>			
Social group	Nr. of interviews	Nr. of interviewees	Audiorecorded
Craftmakers	28	30	26
Policy makers	4	4	4
Schools/educators	1	1	1
Local organizations	5	5	5
Local residents	7	7	7
	45	47	42
<i>Bassano del Grappa</i>			
Social group	Nr. of interviews	Nr. of interviewees	Audiorecorded
Craftmakers	30	26	30
Policy makers	2	2	2
Schools/educators	2	2	2
Local organizations	8	8	8
Local residents	6	6	4
	48	44	46
<i>Venice</i>			
Social group	Nr. of interviews	Nr. of interviewees	Audiorecorded
Craftmakers	30	30	30
Local organizations	7	7	7
Local residents	5	5	5
	42	42	42
Observations			
<i>Events</i>			
<i>Type of event</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Name of the event</i>	<i>Researchers' role</i>
Craft fair	Bornholm	Craft Week	Observation

	Bornholm	European Ceramic Contest 2024	Observation
	Bornholm	SurReal Exhibition	Observation
	Nove	Nove Festa della Ceramica	Observation
	Venice	Fiera dell'Alto Artigianato	Observation
Local gatherings	Dals Långed	Byafest 2024 and 2025	Observation
Industry/interest days	Gothenburg		Observation and participation
	Dals Långed	Craft Days 2024	
<u>Autoethnographies</u>			
	Craftmaker's experiment with motion tracking	1 journal	
	Craftmakers' residencies at FabLab Venice	3 journals	

Ethnographic data analysis

In order to work as an interdisciplinary research team on craft with a shared methodology, we have developed a shared scheme of analysis for the field material. By sharing our intuitions from the fieldwork, we have iterated our empirical initial insights with theories and literature as well as our objectives in HEPHAESTUS. In iterative discussions on the initial interviews among researchers, we have developed a coding scheme, sharing a common social constructivist epistemology (Czarniawska, 2014; Sayes, 2014) and a constructivist understanding of qualitative research methods (Silverman, 2008), in particular grounded theory (Charmaz, 2006; Thornberg and Charmaz, 2014). This scheme was tested on a few pilot interviews during the first period of the project. In the second period, we applied the tested scheme to analyse all remaining and following interviews.

The coding scheme contains 15 broad codes (see Appendix 2 for a description of each code):

1. Life stories of craft makers	9. Place of craft
2. Materials of craft	10. Spaces of craft
3. Making of craft:	11. Skills of craft
4. Selling craft/making craft public	12. Futures of craft
5. Administrating craft	13. Past of craft
6. Labels of craft work/ers	14. Ideas of craft
7. Making a living	15. Critical events

8. Relationships of craft work	
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As part of the analysis process, the researchers involved in fieldwork in each ecosystem have used these codes as broad themes under which they have created specific sub-codes in light of more detailed insights from the interviews and observations and of specificities from each ecosystem. Periodically, we have discussed what emerges from the coding in each ecosystem and across the ecosystems in order to tease out similarities and differences and to develop our understanding of craft and its controversies.

In practical terms, the use of a shared content management system for the interviews has significantly helped the development of the methodology and the use of the coding scheme. The content management system we have used is called DeDoose, and has been an essential step for sharing data and analytical insights. DeDoose is designed and used for analysis of qualitative research data in large collaborative projects. Importantly, this software is compliant with GDPR legislation and has the great advantage of functioning both as an archive and an analytical tool.

Central to the analysis process are also collaborative analysis workshops where researchers from different ecosystems share their preliminary findings based on the coded material as well as concrete ideas for scientific publications. These workshops need to happen at all stages of the analysis and create a developing common understanding of the data collected. This is also crucial for comparison across ecosystems.

2.2.2. Historical methods

As part of the field work, we have also started preparing ourselves to the **historical work** by reading historical literature on craft – some of it shared during the reading group seminars - and on each of the ecosystems. A few readings inspired us particularly. First of all, Adamson’s “The invention of craft” (2013) and “Thinking through craft” (2019). In his work, historian and curator Glenn Adamson explores craft as a social and aesthetic category that has shifted in meaning and boundaries over time. He convincingly argues that craft and industry (and therefore design) are categories that have grown together in relation to each other. So, craft was invented with the industrialization, when a new category of products, production and socio-economic relations came about to which previously existing practices of production could be opposed and complemented: It is around the industrial revolution that the hand and the machine got in opposition to each other, but, as Adamson shows, they have also grown in close relation with each other. Swedish historian Malin Nilsson has studied the early home industry in the textile sector and demonstrated that the relations between the hand and the machine, the work and the capital, craft and industrial products are far more intricate and complex than an opposition (Nilsson, 2015). Methodologically in line with these works, what is paramount for studying craft is to embed the study of contemporary and earlier practices of craft into the socio-economic relations that make them possible and give them value. This means that for the methodology we propose here, it is

important to take a historical approach that sees craft as a result of social, cultural and economic relations and investigate how different versions of craft are produced not only geographically, but also in history, rather than taking craft as a self-explanatory category.

This is in line with historical works in the neo-institutional tradition (e.g. Epstein, 2008; Sabel and Zeitlin, 1985). Challenging deterministic accounts that reduce craft-based organization to anachronism, Epstein (2008) revisits the historiography of European craft guilds, rejecting both the classical dismissal of guilds as rent-seeking obstacles and the revisionist tendency to idealize them. He argues instead for a methodology that foregrounds everyday practices, tacit knowledge, and regionally varied institutional arrangements that allows us to account for variation over time and place and to take craft as a constructed socio-political category. Guilds, he suggests, functioned as adaptive forms of coordination that trained skilled workers, managed risks of innovation, and mediated between artisans, markets, and states. Studying them requires comparative, counterfactual approaches that ask how economies might have evolved without such institutions and that attend to mechanisms like apprenticeship and journey-man mobility. Sabel and Zeitlin (1985) similarly insist that industrial development was not bound to follow a single “narrow track” toward mass production. They highlight the persistence and vitality of alternative paths such as flexible specialization, in which small firms, skilled workers, and multipurpose technologies produced diverse, semi-customized goods. Rather than being technologically inevitable, mass production triumphed through contingent social and political struggles that favored certain arrangements over others. Their methodology emphasizes reconstructing “many-worlds” histories of industrialization, in which different regional, national, and institutional contexts shaped distinct technological trajectories. By showing that guild-like or communitarian forms of production could remain technologically dynamic, they argue that historians must treat technological choice as a political and collective process, not simply as an outcome of efficiency. The encouragement to take diversity in the very socio-economic, cultural and political conditions that produce craft and embed its valuation processes is also in line with recent historical work on entrepreneurship that calls for reinventing the understanding of entrepreneurship in line with other forms of making a living that the dominant capitalist and industrial ones (Wadhvani and Lubinski, 2017).

Taken together, these inspirational historical works serve the purpose of grounding a methodology for studying craft that resists linear or teleological models of craft history and development. This means approaching institutions and practices not as survivals or deviations from an inevitable industrial modernity, but as historically situated alternatives whose viability might offer insights also into a sustainable future. In our historical work, thus, we stress the methodological importance of (1) studying the social category of craft over time in its socio-economic, cultural and political embeddedness as well as of (2) engaging in counterfactual reasoning,

The first methodological path concerning *the embeddedness of the social category of craft* can be achieved in different ways. We stress here the importance of engaging in a conceptual history of craft, which allows to account for our social and cultural categories are constructed rather than given. Such a history implies looking into the evolution of the

etymology of craft in its different linguistic variations, e.g. *hantverk*, *artigianato*, *arte*, *slöjd*. In suggesting conceptual history, we draw particularly on Koselleck's (1982, 2011) notion of *Begriffsgeschichte* to ask whether and how craft can be understood as a concept. For Koselleck, a word becomes a concept when it carries meanings beyond its linguistic form, when its “semantic carrying capacity” extends further than mere usage (1982, p. 410). He distinguishes three types of concepts: traditional concepts, whose meanings remain stable and empirically valid over time; radical concepts, in which meanings change so drastically that they are scarcely comparable despite the continuity of the word; and recurrently emerging neologisms, which arise in response to new circumstances in order to record or provoke them. These distinctions are not fixed, as concepts may shift from one type to another over time.

Conceptual history, as Koselleck outlines it, moves between synchronic and diachronic analysis. The synchronic dimension situates a concept within its immediate contexts of use—its “space of experience” and “horizon of expectation” (p. 415)—reconstructing meanings according to time and place. The diachronic dimension, by contrast, involves translating past usages into present understanding. The strength of this approach lies in its ability to reveal both continuities and fractures: it can register the persistence of past experiences (p. 423), note when meanings have withered and lost their connection to reality, and identify when new realities emerge through concepts whose significance has not yet been fully recognized.

The second methodological historical path is to engage in speculative and counterfactual reasoning. In connection to a central line of work in HEPHAESTUS, we propose art-based methods (e.g. Gasparin, Hjorth & Raviola, 2025) as a way to engage with such a reasoning, not only for academic purposes but also for purposes of participation and engagement with contemporary craft communities. Art-based methods that engage with the “what if” question have also been called upon by social scientists (Gumusay & Reinecke, 2024) as ways to understand both histories and futures in new way. We see these methods as particularly suitable to understand the development of craft because the dominant history, especially economic history, has seen craft as a deviation from industry and an outdated practice.

This counterfactual historical work has been performed in HEPHAESTUS in collaboration with WP3 and the speculative work of the artists' duo D20. Further information and reflection about this method is in WP3's deliverable about the Brave New World.

2.2.3. Design mapping methods.

In recent years, design methods have increasingly made their way into the social sciences and humanities. Indeed, following a broader performativity turn in social research (Muniesa, 2014; Gond and Cabantous, 2015), social scientists across many disciplines have sought new ways to engage with fieldwork in a manner that fully embraces the reality-making capacities of research practice (see Lury & Wakeford, 2012; Marres, Guggenheim & Wilkie, 2018). The performativity turn put on display how research is a practice that is not simply representing or capturing the making of realities on the ground, but it is also contributing to the making of the realities it seeks to represent. Seeing social science as a matter

of both representation and intervention has paved the way for a rapprochement between established methods in social research and creative practices and techniques from artistic disciplines such as design (Pink, 2014; Hjorth et al., 2019). Importantly, the methodological implications of performativity are irreducible to prescription; rather, they open inquiries to be conducted in a more experimental key in a manner that steers away from explanatory closure, which entails both an epistemic and aesthetic engagement with the field (Marres, Guggenheim & Wilkie, 2018).

Within design research, and more specifically “research-through-design” or “design practice research” (Kaszynska & Kimbell, 2024), the role of methods is interventionist through and through as it involves participation in acts of making. Through making *in* and *as* fieldwork, researchers devise material experiments and modes of collaboration, creating conditions to learn and inquire with others (Criado & Estalella, 2018). Against this conceptual and practical background, our project mobilizes design methods to investigate and engage with our ecosystems and its actors, particularly through design mapping approaches. Such designerly approaches to mapping offer researchers a different way to engage with empirical material by working in a dynamic and visual way, calling attention to what emerges between the lines and spaces of a mapping (Schumack, 2014), not simply as a tool for epistemic representation but also as a tool for aesthetic activation. In our project we combine this designerly way of mapping with an established mapping approach in the social sciences, namely controversy mapping (also known as the cartography of controversies) (Venturini & Munk, 2022).

The cartography of controversies is a mapping approach developed in the field of science and technology studies (STS) that was originally conceived by Bruno Latour as a pedagogical tool to introduce students to actor-network theory (ANT) at the Center for the Sociology of Innovation in École des Mines in Paris (Venturini, 2010). Nowadays, however, this form of mapping is now established as a research method in its own right and used across many disciplines beyond STS (Venturini, 2010; Venturini & Munk, 2022), including architecture (Yaneva, 2010; Yaneva & Heaphy, 2012), education sciences (Elam, Solli & Mäkitalo, 2018), organization studies (Tureta, Américo & Clegg, 2021; Américo, Tureta & Clegg, 2025), and design (Venturini et al., 2015) among others. Controversy mapping departs from the premise that controversies are key sites to investigate society in the making. In other words, controversies reveal the fabric of social life since, in debating and solving public disputes around a particular issue (technoscientific or otherwise), actors are engaged in the weaving and unweaving of relations, and the construction and negotiation of identities and categories (Venturini, 2010). As a method, controversy mapping has acquired a very procedural character following the prescriptions of its main contemporary proponents (Venturini & Munk, 2022; Venturini, 2010). For instance, Venturini et al. (2015) offer the following steps for the mapping and analysis of controversies with the aid of digital tools:

1. *From statements to debates (what)*

The goal here is to show that statements in controversies are never isolated but always connected in a dialogue made of endorsements and oppositions. What are the statements that help us characterize and delineate the existence of the debate?

2. *From debates to actors (who)*

The goal here is to attach statements to their speakers. Who says what? Who shares which argument with whom?

3. *From actors to networks (how)*

The goal here is to show how actors are connected to other actors and enrolled in networks of relations formed around particular interests. On whose behalf are the actors speaking? What actor-networks are being formed in the course of the controversy?

4. *From networks to cosmoeses (where)*

The goal here is to situate the controversy within larger meta-controversies and also identify the sub-controversies of which it is composed. Beyond the particular interests at stake in a given controversy, what worldviews, utopias or ideologies are animating actors or groups involved?

5. *From cosmoeses to cosmopolitics (when)*

The goal here is to show how controversies evolve through time. How do opposing camps and perspectives shift over time? How does the introduction of new elements (pieces of evidence, technologies, etc.) into the controversy shape its course?

Others have sought to adapt the method in a less procedural manner. For instance, in their study of public administration practices in the context of a hospital contract controversy in Brazil, Tureta and colleagues (2021) use controversy mapping as a historical method. They propose five non-linear focal points to structure fieldwork for controversy analysis:

- Identifying controversies
- Mapping the actor-network
- Tracing the translation process
- Labelling the politics of actor-networks
- Describing the multiple reality and power relations

In the context of our project, our third methodological pillar blends principles from the cartography of controversies with design mapping. In this sense, our aim is not so much procedurally “applying” controversy mapping as it is inventively engaging with its principles in a designerly manner. We build on a diverse range of design methods that imply a varying degree of participatory practices and of aesthetic production (Schranz, 2021; de la Rosa et al., 2021). These methods are interwoven with the previous methodological pillars in the

sense that they build on their results, while at the same time preparing for new iterations of those methods.

Our methodology expands the STS controversy mapping process to include inspiration from multimodal anthropology (Westmoreland, 2021) and design studies (Venturini et al., 2015) and we have worked on new ways of mapping which are both grounded in analytical coding of our field material and designed in aesthetic ways that open for moments of wonder, thinking and dialoguing unexpected and novel aspects of craft. From the coding we realized that the most fruitful way to map controversies was to choose a site-specific controversy for each ecosystem in order to manifest concretely a larger controversy in the craft world. The design methods useful in this third pillar are different and we recognize at least three:

- I) Participatory mapping workshops – visually identifying controversies
- II) Reflexive workshops – articulating controversies
- III) Map-activating workshop – articulating, unfolding and acting on controversies

(I) Participatory mapping workshops – visually identifying controversies

We printed different types of geographical maps of the ecosystems and through participatory design methods we asked the craftmakers to situate on the maps their working spaces, their relations and their desired avenues of development.

Figure 8 – Iterative mapping workshops in Dals Långed.

Figure 9 – Mapping workshop in Bassano del Grappa

A form of innovative mapping method that took craftmakers’ participation to the next level (much beyond conventional participatory design) was the participatory exhibition about tools and objects of crafts that we organized across the ecosystems. This exhibition responded to two issues that emerged in the ethnographic work: firstly, the importance of tools and low-technologies in craft work, especially in relation to the craft-specific relationship with material and in relation to the project’s and policy’s interest in cutting-edge technologies; secondly, the desire of craftmakers to shape their own narratives not only in their own communities, but also towards policy makers and the public. So, given these emerging issues, we engaged three curators among the craft ambassadors of the local Swedish ecosystem and they initiated a collaborative process with the other craftmakers in the other ecosystems to bring together the voice of craftmakers. The result was the exhibition *Semblance: Makers*

and Their Tool , exhibited during the Craft Days of West Sweden at the prestigious Röhsska Museum of Design and Craft.

The exhibition showed 20 objects from the four craft ecosystems and the tools with which they were made. By empowering the craftmakers to make their own narrative, this exhibition was a milestone in the HEPHAESTUS project in building cross-country exchanges among craftmakers (and not only researchers), creating legitimacy for the project in practice and unfolding the craft-makers self-narratives.

Figure 10 – *Semblance* participatory exhibition posters

Figure 11 – *Semblance* exhibition showing craftmakers’s objects and tools.

(II) Reflexive workshops – articulating controversies, “talking by doing”

The second workshop that uses participatory methods aimed at reflection and the articulation of some of these controversies is the creation of reflection spaces in a non-academic contexts. We have called this “talking by doing” and includes different forms of making individually and collectively (for example, we have worked with postcards sent to us in between workshops, with writing to one-self and with chatGPT collective writing). Conceptually, we explore this method as a process of co-crafting that offers alternatives to co-design (Hansson & von Busch, 2023).

We designed this kind of workshop in a wide variety of occasions in HEPHAESTUS and it has served as a fundamental element of our controversy mapping. We have done it in single ecosystems as well as by bringing craft ambassadors of different ecosystems together. We have involved 4-6 craft ambassadors – as well as other craftmakers – in different participatory workshops using participatory design methods. In a series of workshops in Sweden, in Bassano and in Bornholm, we have developed participatory design methods to focus on the following themes: community engagement and relation to the local economy; sustainability and circularity; new technologies. Each of these themes provide material for developing innovative business models for craft.

In fact, one part of our yearly meeting at the end of year 1 and year 2 have been explicitly and fruitfully dedicated to this kind of workshop. Expanding the task from the official description (where one craft workshop involving researchers and craftmakers was planned in month 8), we organized co-crafting workshops both at the end of year 1 and at the end of year 2 with the large HEPHAESTUS community of craftmakers, policy makers and researchers. During month 14 of the project, we organized a 4 days-workshop with craftmakers and us researchers together to both discuss their and our work and allow them to perform their craft and share knowledge about their techniques in Sweden and in month 27 of the project we organized a 3 days symposium in Bornholm, including co-crafting. These co-crafting workshops allowed the craft makers to share traditional techniques and processes, such as willow-weaving, rope making and potato printing, but it also allowed to explore new connections and machines, like the ceramic-crushing machine in Bornholm.

Figure 12 – Craft exchanges in talking and doings in craft workshop in Dals Långed.

Figure 13 – Craft exchanges in talking and doing (rope making) in craft workshop in Bornholm, June 2025.

Several co-crafting workshops were grounded in the intention to further explore findings from the interviews. One of the main themes in our ethnographies has been the social value of craft in relation to a specific place: Craft has appear in our findings as a central practice

in the making of commonalities and common spaces in a specific space. So, we tested a series of co-crafting workshops aimed at reflecting and discussing this specific meaning of craft. For instance, we explored this in a collaborative workshop, we developed in August 2024 in Dals Långed, Sweden. Together with design professor Otto von Busch from Parson School of Design, we invited local craft makers and researchers to co-craft public furniture in a common space in the forest. Our aim was to explore the social, cultural and political value of craft in a collective and performative way (Hansson & von Busch, 2023; Raviola et al., 2023). Another occasion was a co-craft workshop to make a common space at the Academy of Art and Design in Gothenburg, and at Parson School of Design in New York. In both places, craft and design students were involved together with researchers and craft makers in a co-crafting process, led by Helena Hansson.

A specific note here is to be developed in relation to the investigation of gender gaps in craft work in the different ecosystems. From our ethnographic work, genders appeared as an important theme, although not the primary source of concerns from craftmakers. In different ecosystems, some craftmakers made gender an explicit object of intervention in order to change the gender stereotypes of craft and produce safe space for minority groups that do not normally have access to craft. In the spirit of our methodology, we thus followed up this concern from our ethnographic work with a design-based workshop. In March 2024, in Dals Långed, we invited a local wood-based craftmaker working with gender and safe spaces to hold a “talking by doing” - co-crafting work with other local craftmakers, educators and researchers. This raised the issue of intersectionality both in craft practice and in craft education. Concomitantly with this design workshop, we also organized a co-creation workshop related to WP4 and researchers from WP4 were present at the gender design workshop, so that they could integrate into their educational toolbox.

A third important occasion to explore co-crafting for a common space has been the work that we have engaged with in Dals Långed in relation to a site called Open Wood. This work intersects the theme of the common space with that of new technologies from our ethnographic work and explores site-specific relationships between them in our Swedish ecosystem. In the ecosystem of Dals Långed, this is manifested in Open Wood, an old industrial site that is reused in a collaboration between the Academy, craft makers and industry to make furniture with new technologies in sustainable ways. The main controversies that unfold locally around Open Wood mirror a larger controversy between craft and technologies, hands and codes, but also mobilize the social role of craft in building common spaces. So, we have developed a specific methodology for mapping site-specific controversies that we present below.

(III) Map-activating workshops – articulating, unfolding and acting on site-specific controversies

The shared analysis of the field material from ethnographies, historical paths and design methods, has been the springboard to identify site-specific controversies and develop a method to work with them.

Drawing on controversy mapping as a method, we explored the project Open Wood as a site-specific controversy within the Dals Långed-Fengersfors ecosystem. Open Wood is a publicly funded initiative which revolves around the creation and running of a state-of-the-art experimental wood workshop in Dals Långed. This initiative is part of a larger effort involving public and private actors aimed at establishing a local infrastructure for craft-driven regional development and, more recently, for renewal of traditional craft production with new technologies. Such an effort has been supported by both the regional government and industry through consistent investment and funding of projects and initiatives in the area, such as Open Wood. This workshop features advanced equipment, operating as an innovation environment with a view to facilitating the transition towards a more sustainable furniture industry. However, during our fieldwork, it became apparent that the introduction of new machines and equipment for experimental wood manufacturing, as well as the question of who gets to experiment and for what purpose, generated much ambivalence among craft makers working in the area. We, therefore, set out to analyze this situation as a site-specific controversy that could shed light on the relation between craft and new technology via a designerly approach to controversy mapping. In other words, we sought to visually examine what happens when craft making meets new technologies and the space and meaning of manual and mechanical work need to be negotiated.

The mapping process began with the exploration and discussion among the research team of what might constitute “data” for our incipient controversy map. We speculatively came up with potential map legends that could inform our exploration. Different categories came to the fore in this process, including location, finances, flows of people and materials, among other things, but this was only used as a brainstorming exercise to open possible avenues for our exploration. That said, our visual point of departure was the location map of the site where the Open Wood workshop is in Dals Långed, including its immediate surroundings, which was retrieved from Google Maps. Our analytic point of departure was the interview material (35 transcribed interviews). We gathered quotes from all the instances where Open Wood was mentioned by our interviewees. We printed these quotes and laid them out on a long paper roll (3 meters long). Then, following Venturini et al. (2015), we identified statements of what Open Wood could or should be, tracking also who was behind specific statements. We used markers of different colors to physically highlight on the paper roll the identified statements, using yellow for mentions of the ‘who’s’ and orange for mentions of the ‘what’. We attached keywords to the highlighted statements using sticky notes. Some examples include “green”, “circular”, “meeting place”, “go and test”, “machine”, “advanced tech”, “collaboration.”

In the second iteration of this map, quotes were arranged in a new roll and organized with hashtags corresponding to the identified codes. Statements from the quotes were also simplified and paraphrased to adjust to the formulation ‘Open Wood is...’ The researcher leading the mapping triangulated these paraphrases with the researchers who interviewed and coded the interview material to corroborate these interpretive moves. We continued to re-code statements to refine the analysis by, for instance, identifying which statements were about students, money, research, tools, network, time, etc. We thought of these categories as representing ‘matters of concern’ for the actors involved.

Figure 14 – Visualization of the mapping process in media res.

Figure 15 - Map Legend

Table 2 presents some examples on different design workshops run in HEPHAESTUS.

TABLE 2 - Examples of design workshop			
Workshop type	Location	Main purpose	Main participants
Mapping	Dals Långed	Iterative mapping of the ecosystem and its relationships	Craftmakers
	Bornholm	Initial mapping of the ecosystem and its relationships	Craftmakers and policy makers
	Bassano del Grappa	Initial mapping of the ecosystem and its relationships	Craftmakers and policy makers
	Nove	Initial mapping of the ecosystem and its relationships	Craftmakers and policy makers
Talking by doing	Dals Långed	Paper making	Local craftmakers and researchers
	Dals Långed	Potato printing	Selected craftmakers from all ecosystems, researchers and policy makers
	Dals Långed	Willow weaving	Selected craftmakers from all ecosystems
	Dals Långed	Stone and technology	Local craftmakers and Fablab Venice
	Gothenburg	Rope making and wood carving	Public, craftmakers, policymakers
Site-specific controversy mapping	Dals Långed	Open Wood	Series of workshop for Open Wood craftmakers and other local craftmakers during the Fall 2025. Purpose is to unravel

and activation	the relationship with new technologies and find a new organizational model for a shared workshop.
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2.3. Combination of the three methodological pillars

The three pillars of our methodology – ethnographic methods, historical methods and design mapping methods – are combined in our proposed and experimented methodology in multiple ways that allow iterating between different kinds of empirical material and different modes of interaction between the researchers and the field. Rather than keeping the researchers in an ivory tower of knowledge and objectifying practitioners, our methodology is grounded in an ethical standing that brings together rigorous and systematic production of scientific knowledge and respect for practitioners’ knowledges and understandings as well as their ability to participate to the validation of scientific results and projection into future developments.

In our use of the methodology and in the participatory spirit of HEPHAESTUS, we have started and ended with design methods (see figure 13), which has allowed us to get input from craft practitioners and policy makers on the urgent issues on the ground since the beginning of the project, has given us legitimacy to access the field and has created the space for making the results relevant not only at the national and European policy level, but also, importantly, at the regional and local level as well as for empowering craft practitioners to have new perspectives on their own field and project new solutions to their urgencies. If design methods have allowed us entrance and exit from the field, they have been enriched, transformed and grounded in ethnographic and historical methods, which have allowed us to generate material that is scientifically solid and able to give new insights not only to the scientific community but also to practitioners.

Figure 16 – Combination of the three methodological pillars.

The temporality of the iterations of our different pillars might be different in different research projects, but we see the combination of the three methodological pillars as valid for research projects that seek to investigate the values of creative and cultural work, especially the type of work which bears a strong historical significance. In our own work, we have worked on weaving different paths of iteration through different points of entry. In figure 13, we represent some of these paths, without being exhaustive, to offer readers the idea of different ways of combining the different pillars.

Figure 17 – Different paths of combination of the three pillars.

3. Results: analysis of the controversies across the ecosystems of HEPHAESTUS

After presenting our methodology, we turn to the specific results of its application in HEPHAESTUS. The results presented in this report bring together the historical, cultural, and contemporary mappings of the four selected craft ecosystems—Venice, Bassano del Grappa, Bornholm, and Dals Långed. The findings highlight both continuities and transformations in the role of craft across time, as well as the pressing urgencies that currently shape these ecosystems. By combining historical and ethnographic perspectives with controversy mapping, the analysis foregrounds the interconnections between heritage, sustainability, and digitisation.

The results are organised in three parts. The *first* part traces the historical and contemporary identity of each ecosystem, situating craft within its material and cultural conditions of possibility as well as in relation to the socio-economic and cultural infrastructures that underpin the functioning of the craft ecosystems. The *second* part turns to controversies, identifying the debates and tensions that define the present and future of craft, particularly in relation to sustainability, the adoption of new technologies and livelihood. In this part, we capture the current urgencies of craft ecosystems, as voiced by the members of the ecosystem, especially in relation to sustainability and digitization, and unpack how members of the ecosystem manifest resistance or acceptance of both digital and cutting-edge technologies and sustainability actions. The *third* part offers a comparative picture of how craft is negotiated, valued, and contested in different European contexts in relation to the three areas of urgencies and controversies identified and visualizes each ecosystem in terms of their values towards those controversial areas.

3.1. Historical identity and contemporary infrastructures

Our historical work, whose methodological learnings and groundings were presented and discussed in the previous section of this report, has provided the basis for capturing the historical identity of the ecosystems in focus in HEPHAESTUS and, in combination with the ethnography of field-configuring events and craft practices, it has allowed us to understand the contemporaneity of the ecosystems in a historically grounded yet today-relevant way. Through ethnographic methods, we have in fact mapped the current infrastructures in each ecosystems, e.g. the institutions, socio-economic structures, atmospheres. The combination of ethnographic and historical methods here has thus allowed us to see the ‘cultures of craft’ emerging in the different ecosystems and account for the multiplicity that lies behind the overarching term of ‘craft’, which our results suggest risks of flattening the richness and variety of conditions of practice in different regional cultures and economies, while allowing the possibility to create a collectivity at the national and European policy level.

Understanding the historical trajectories of the craft ecosystems is not only a matter of documenting past practices of craft and their understandings, but also of safeguarding cultural heritage as a living and evolving resource. UNESCO highlights that intangible

cultural heritage, including craftsmanship, depends on its continuous transmission and adaptation to changing contexts (UNESCO, 2003). At the same time, European policy recognises heritage as a driver for identity, belonging, and sustainable development (European Commission, 2014). By tracing materials, practices, and socio-economic embeddedness across time, our mapping contributes to the safeguarding of these heritages while also illuminating points of fragility—such as loss of knowledge, environmental pressures, or shifts in production—that risk undermining their continuity. In this sense, the historical analysis provides an essential foundation for understanding contemporary urgencies and for rethinking how craft heritage can be renewed.

Our historical work in each ecosystem resonates with broader UNESCO’s international frameworks for classifying risk for intangible cultural heritage (see also earlier discussion in the introduction of this report), inasmuch as it identifies key vulnerabilities for craft heritage continuity (UNESCO, n.d.). Our findings across the four ecosystems reflect these risks in concrete ways: the decline in transmission of skills and apprenticeships in Bornholm illustrates demographic pressures; scarcity of raw materials and pollution from former industrial operations in Dals Långed aligns with environmental concerns; while the impact of mass production and global markets in Venice with its hypertourism, and Bassano del Grappa points to the pressures of cultural globalisation. In Bassano and Nove, the issue of the family legacy and transmission of skills is also highly relevant.

Through this work we have thus captured the historical and contemporary identity of craft and observed the craft ecosystems’ socio-economic and cultural infrastructures in the making (not only historically). We present the results of this work by (I) first elaborating on our conceptual history of craft and (II) then by presenting the historical identity and contemporary infrastructures of each of the four ecosystems in focus in HEPHAESTUS, i.e. Venice, Bassano del Grappa (and Nove), Bornholm and Dals Långed (and Fengersfors). While these results are specific to our ecosystems, the conceptual history of craft has more general ambitions.

3.1.1. A conceptual history of craft

In modern history, craft occupied a subordinate position compared to art, as seen for example in the British Arts and Crafts movement, and it became further marginalized during the industrialization of the nineteenth century (Popp & Holt, 2016).

The word *craft* originates in the Germanic languages, cognate with Frisian *krefte* and Old High German *Kraft*. Its earliest meaning was “strength, power, might,” a sense still present in Old English until the early sixteenth century. From the Middle English period onward (around the twelfth century), *craft* gradually took on meanings such as skill, dexterity, art, and talent, extending also to occupations that required manual expertise acquired through practice and learning. This semantic shift was reinforced after the Norman conquest, when *craft* began to translate the Latin *ars* via contact with Old and Middle French *art*. In this way, *craft* acquired a wide semantic range that included method, technique, skill, trade, and

profession, as well as associations with the liberal and fine arts. While *art* and *craft* overlapped for centuries, they began to diverge between the fifteenth and seventeenth centuries: *art* came to emphasize imagination, intellect, and creativity, while *craft* remained tied to technical and manual skills. Even earlier, in Greek thought, the concept closest to craft was *tekhnē*, meaning the art of making something present and usable—a chair, a crop, or even a divine word (Cooper, 1993; Shiner, 2001).

By the early nineteenth century, *craft* had also acquired pejorative connotations of deception or cunning, especially in relation to industrial society. Yet by the end of that century, amid a revival of traditional practices, it came to signify skilled manual work and, more generally, activities involving hand-making and traditional techniques (Sennett, 2008). One important meaning that persisted through this history is that of *trade*, recalling the institutional forms of organization—guilds and corporations—through which crafts were practiced. Craft guilds, widespread across Europe, functioned not only as associations of artisans but also as social, civic, and religious bodies (Bisgaard et al., 2013). Their main roles included political representation, regulating markets and quality standards, protecting smaller competitors, and overseeing apprenticeship systems that allowed workers to progress to master status (Epstein & Prak, 2008). In the medieval and early modern city, guilds were central to urban life, and workshops combined domestic, productive, and educational functions. Despite the rise of industrialization, guilds remained influential well into the nineteenth century, and their abolition was driven more by political than strictly economic motives (Epstein & Prak, 2008).

According to Adamson (2013), although craft as practice is historically constant, its emergence as a coherent idea should be located between 1750 and 1850, when it arose as a counterpoint to the rationalization and mechanization of industrial production. The dichotomy between tradition and innovation that shapes contemporary conceptions of craft has its roots in this period, culminating in the Arts and Crafts movement founded in 1887. Inspired by Ruskin and Morris, the movement criticized industrial labor for its alienation and loss of meaning, advocating instead for the craftsman as a free and creative worker. Yet this vision idealized pre-industrial craft, overlooking the fact that workshop labor also involved division of tasks, albeit in less alienating ways (Shiner, 2001; Popp and Holt, 2016). It contributed to a romanticized image of the maker while shifting the role of the artist towards entrepreneurial independence and market-driven recognition.

Later reinterpretations of craft can be seen in what Jakob (2013) calls its “waves.” The first wave corresponds to its eighteenth- and nineteenth-century redefinition; the second emerged within the countercultural movements of the 1960s and 1970s; and the third reflects the renewed interest in craft today. Recent ideas of *neo-craft* (Gandini and Gerosa, 2023) resonate with concerns about de-alienation, sustainability, and the search for more embodied and material forms of work (Rosa, 2003). Neo-craft emphasizes quality materials, traditional practices, and slower, more situated forms of life, often in rural contexts, in deliberate contrast to industrial mass production and accelerated urban lifestyles. In a similar vein, Micelli (2011) presents craftsmanship as a re-humanizing practice that reclaims material engagement, while Sennett (2008) emphasizes the philosophical dimensions of craft as a way of working that encompasses a broad range of occupations.

The challenge for a conceptual history of craft lies in tracing how these meanings shift across languages and contexts. In this research, the analysis is conducted in English, yet the field sites—Bornholm and Dals Långed—operate within Danish and Swedish contexts. Here, terms such as *håndværk* or *slöjd* carry their own social, cultural, and political resonances, which cannot be assumed to map directly onto the English *craft*. Exploring these differences is central to understanding how craft is conceptualized and practiced in specific contexts.

3.1.2 Historical identity and contemporary infrastructures of craft ecosystems

A brief craft history of the Venetian ecosystem

The history of Venetian craft is deeply intertwined with the city's strategic position and long-standing maritime tradition. Venice's rise as a center of craftsmanship began with its privileged access to trade routes, particularly those connecting Europe with the East via the Silk Road. Through these exchanges, Venetian merchants brought home precious raw materials like silks, spices, and minerals, stimulating the development of luxury goods industries. The city's unique lagoon environment and its dependence on seaborne commerce also encouraged innovation and a self-sufficient economy, in which crafts played a central role.

By the Middle Ages, Venice had already formed craft guilds, known as *Arti*. These guilds were mutual associations of artisans specializing in particular trades. Membership often began at a young age, with boys entering as apprentices and gradually advancing through the ranks. These guilds maintained strict standards for production quality and passed down intricate techniques through generations, preserving the city's artisanal excellence. In some cases, these techniques were even considered state secrets, highlighting their economic and strategic value.

The following crafts particularly flourished in Venice:

Murano Glass: Though glassmaking existed in Venice prior to the 13th century, it was in 1291 that the city's glass furnaces were officially moved to the island of Murano. This relocation was largely a fire-prevention measure, as the open flames used in glass production posed serious threats to the wooden structures of central Venice. Murano glassmakers clustered in this island and developed an extraordinary variety of techniques—such as *filigrana*, *reticello*, and *aventurina*—that set their creations apart. From elegant goblets and chandeliers to intricate beads and sculptures, Murano glass became a symbol of luxury across Europe. The master glassmakers were so esteemed that they were granted special privileges, but also forbidden from leaving the Republic to prevent the leakage of their trade secrets.

Burano Lace: Another jewel in Venice's artisanal crown is Burano lace. The origins of this delicate craft are linked to fishing communities, where women adapted net-making techniques into ornamental lacework. Over time, lace production evolved into a refined art, practiced by noblewomen, nuns, and working-class women alike. Burano lace became so coveted that it competed with—and sometimes surpassed—the famous lace industries of

Flanders, England, and France. The intricate designs, crafted entirely by hand, reflected countless hours of labor and deep generational knowledge. Today, although the number of lace-makers has declined, the tradition remains alive through local workshops and museums that celebrate this unique cultural heritage.

Carnival Masks and Costumes: The Carnival of Venice is known worldwide for its mystery and pageantry, and at the heart of this tradition lies the craft of mask-making. Venetian masks, often made of papier-mâché, porcelain, or leather, have their roots in medieval festivities and were historically used not only during Carnival but also in daily life to disguise identity for political or social reasons. Each mask has its own symbolism and history, from the *Bauta* to the *Moretta*, and the artistry involved in their creation includes sculpting, painting, gilding, and costume design. Although modern mask-making is largely aimed at tourists, some artisans continue to honor historical methods and materials, keeping the tradition alive, following the recovery of historical techniques related to the modern revival of Carnival since 1979 .

Textiles: The production of luxury textiles, especially velvet and brocade, flourished in Venice thanks to both imported materials and local innovation. Venetian looms produced richly patterned fabrics that were exported across Europe and used in aristocratic garments and ecclesiastical vestments.

Jewelry: crafted exquisite pieces using gold, enamel, and Murano glass beads. These items were not merely accessories but cultural signifiers, often worn during religious or civic ceremonies.

Throughout the centuries, the Venetian Republic was keenly aware of the economic and symbolic power of its crafts. Techniques and recipes were closely guarded, and the artisans' knowledge was transmitted through tightly controlled apprenticeships. The government even enacted laws to prevent skilled workers from emigrating, recognizing that the departure of one master could mean the loss of an entire trade. This system of protection helped ensure the survival of traditional methods well into the modern era. Today, Venetian craftsmanship is recognized not only for its artistic value but also as a cornerstone of intangible cultural heritage. Workshops, foundations, and artisan associations continue to pass down ancient skills, bridging past and present.

Evidence of Venice's artisanal legacy is etched into its very geography. Street names near the Rialto Market and San Marco recall the trades once practiced there: *Calle dei Fabri* (blacksmiths), *Calle del Tentor* (dyers), *Calle dei Saoneri* (soap-makers), and *Calle della Frezaria* (arrow-makers), to name a few.

Old Scuole (guild houses) still stand as testaments to these trades, such as the *Scuola dei Battiloro* (gold beaters) in San Stae or the *Scuola dei Calagheri* (shoemakers) in San Tomà. Even today, visitors can witness living tradition in places like the *Squero di San Trovaso*, where gondolas are built and repaired, or the *Orsoni mosaic workshop* in Cannaregio, preserving the art of Venetian terrazzo floors. Organizations like *El Felze*, which supports the artisans involved in gondola construction, and ongoing efforts to protect traditional trades

from mass tourism and globalization pressures, demonstrate the enduring relevance of these crafts.

While many trades thrived for centuries, others have faced decline. One such example is the blacksmithing tradition. Venetian *favari* (ironworkers) once played a crucial role in the city's economy, crafting everything from tools to decorative railings. But by the 18th century, competition from mainland ironworkers—who had access to cheaper raw materials—undermined Venetian production. Despite the flourishing of cast-iron foundries in the 19th century, the trade gradually shifted toward ornamental work, and today only a handful of smithies remain.

A brief craft history of the ecosystem of Bassano del Grappa and Nove

Nestled in the foothills of the Venetian Prealps, the towns of Bassano del Grappa and Nove have long been known for their deep-rooted artisanal traditions. Located in the province of Vicenza, in the Veneto region of northern Italy, these towns developed unique identities through centuries of craftsmanship, particularly in the production of ceramics, woodworking, engraving, and other decorative arts.

The artisan culture of Bassano and Nove developed in part thanks to the natural wealth of the Brenta River Valley. The Brenta River provided not only transport routes for goods and materials but also essential energy for water mills and early workshops. Moreover, the rich clay deposits in the area, particularly around Nove, were key to the rise of the local ceramics industry. Bassano, with its strategic location between Venice and the Alps, became a hub of commerce and artistic exchange since the Renaissance. Meanwhile, Nove—its smaller neighbor—grew around its potteries and kilns, and by the end of the 18th century had become one of Italy's most important ceramic centers.

The specificities of Nove

The town of Nove is almost synonymous with **ceramics**. The name itself comes from the Latin *novae terrae* (new lands), referring to the fertile, clay-rich soil of the Brenta River plain. Since the 17th century, artisans in Nove have shaped, painted, and fired clay into both everyday objects and artistic masterpieces.

Ceramics production in Nove began in earnest in the early 18th century, strongly influenced by the nearby Venetian Republic and its appetite for decorative arts. Local families like the Antonibon and Baccin became known for their high-quality majolica and porcelain, often decorated with floral motifs, mythological scenes, and oriental influences, following European tastes of the time. The Antonibon manufactory, founded in the 1720s, played a crucial role in raising Nove's reputation throughout Europe. The quality and innovation of its pieces made them highly sought after by noble families and even royal courts.

Nove ceramics are celebrated for their varied decorative styles, ranging from baroque excess to neoclassical elegance. Artisans mastered both majolica (tin-glazed

pottery) and porcelain, employing complex painting and glazing techniques. Many of these traditional methods are still used today in local workshops. After a crisis following the fall of the Venetian Republic, in the 19th and early 20th centuries, the craft evolved to incorporate Art Nouveau and Art Deco influences, ensuring the continued relevance of Nove's ceramics on the global stage.

Today, Nove remains a center of ceramic excellence. It hosts the Museo della Ceramica, located in the historic Palazzo De' Fabris, which preserves centuries of ceramic history, and an High School focusing on applied arts established in 1875. Despite the crisis of the ceramic industrial district that flourished until the 1980s, local artisans continue to produce high-end, hand-decorated pieces, and international collectors still visit Nove to purchase authentic, handmade ceramics.

The specificities of Bassano del Grappa

While Nove focused on ceramics, Bassano del Grappa developed a more diversified artisanal economy, deeply influenced by the Renaissance, the Venetian dominion, and the intellectual atmosphere of the 16th century. The main crafts that flourished in Bassano are:

Woodworking and Furniture: Bassano's surrounding forests provided ample timber, which fostered the growth of a sophisticated woodworking industry. In the 17th and 18th centuries, Bassano became known for its elegant furniture, carved wooden objects, and turned wood pieces. The region was particularly skilled in producing inlaid wooden furniture and decorative pieces, often inspired by Venetian Rococo styles. The knowledge of wood carving and intarsia has been recovered thanks to Bussandri, a wealthy antiquarian who started the production of furniture with ancient techniques in the 1930s. During the economic miracle, several of his wood workers started making artistic furniture in what became a specialised district.

Printing and Engraving: One of the most remarkable chapters in Bassano's artisanal history is its contribution to printing and engraving, thanks to the Remondini family. From the late 17th century to the mid 19th century, the Remondini Press became one of the largest and most influential printing houses in Europe. They printed everything from religious images and prayer cards to maps, books, and wallpaper, often using innovative techniques such as woodblock printing and copperplate engraving. The Remondinis employed hundreds of workers, including engravers, typesetters, and binders, and their products reached as far as Russia and South America. Their workshop was not only a business as they also established a School of engraving, which continued in the late 19th century with municipal funding. The legacy of the Remondinis is preserved in the Palazzo Sturm Museum of Printing of Bassano del Grappa, which houses a vast collection of prints, books, and tools from the period, and in the Grafiche Tassotti shop, whose founder also collected materials from the Remondinis and reproduced their decorations in his production of paper objects.

Ceramics: Though not as central as in Nove, ceramics production was present in Bassano since the late 1600s century, and workers from the Manardi's factory in Bassano were moving to Nove in the subsequent century. In the late 1800s, following the decline of

production in Nove, new ceramic factories were established in Bassano. They specialised in the eclectic reinterpretation of rococo-style maiolicas, much appreciated since the end of the 19th century in International expositions and markets.

A brief craft history of the Bornholm ecosystem

Bornholm, first island in Europe to have been awarded with the title of World Craft Region, is distinguished today by the presence of several craftmakers and artists. Whilst today the island hosts ceramists, glass blowers, textile, wood, and metal makers and artists, the strong presence of a tradition of and engagement in making practices has historical roots. Indeed, not only some making practices, such as pottery and ceramic, endured over time changing and adapting according to the circumstances, but the makers of the island could exploit even the most unusual circumstances in the past. An emblematic case, in this sense, is the over-a-century lasting production of ‘grandfather clocks’, started in 1744 after a Dutch ship stranded off the coasts of the island: among other things, the ship carried longcase clocks. As a group of capable turners have been enlisted to dry, clean and grease the clocks, not a long time passed before some makers decided to produce original clocks themselves and ship them all over Europe, inaugurating a trade that lasted until the early 1890s.

Among the many craft practices that are active nowadays on the island – ceramics, glass blowing, textile, wood, and metal works – ceramic’s history on Bornholm is the richest. While being present throughout Bornholm’s history, the ceramic sector started to expand significantly around the end of the Eighteenth Century. In particular, with the opening of Johan Spietz’s stoneware factory in the late 1700s, and of other factories during the Nineteenth and the Twentieth century as Søholm Keramik (1835–1996), Hjorths Fabrik (1859-today active as a factory in a small capacity and a museum), Michael Andersen & Søn (1873), Bofa Ceramics (1862-1961), and Johgus (1940s) (among others), prevalently in the city of Rønne, Bornholm assumed a relevant and visible role in the ceramic sector in Europe. The factories operated employing craftsmakers to produce objects that were exported in Europe, and usually craftmakers had the possibility, while working in the factories, to experiment and develop their own language. Factories productions spanned from daily use objects as dishware, crates, vases and jars to decorations to be integrated with the architecture of the island. Whilst most factories closed throughout the Twentieth century, ceramists kept working on the island, and some arrived to the island drawn by the nature of the place and the interests in ceramic. During the second half of the 1900s glass blowing emerged in Bornholm as well.

Besides the professional environment, Bornholm started to attract students in ceramics and glass blowing with the establishment in 1997 of the School of Glass and Ceramics on Bornholm in the town of Nexø, an independent educational institution that offered three-years programme with a qualification equivalent to a bachelor’s degree. In 2010 the school merged with the Danish Design School, becoming a unit of older and larger The Royal Danish Academy of Arts (Det Kongelige Akademi), remaining in Nexø. Between the end of the Twentieth century and the first decades of the present one, workshops and small

factories opened in Nexø or close towns as Svaneke and Allinge. The new school offered both bachelor's and master's programme, although in the last year the offering has been reduced again to the bachelor programme only, as per decisions made by the Copenhagen's unit of the Academy, as consequence of overall educational decisions made by the Danish Government.

Craftmakers today are mostly part of the local arts and craft association, ACAB (Arts and Craft Association Bornholm). The association owns a shop in Allinge, collecting a large selection of handmade products of the Island, and organises annual exhibitions at Grønbechs Gård, the Bornholm's Center for Kunsthåndværk (Arts and Craft) located in Hasle. ACAB has been determinant in the establishment of Bornholm as World Craft Region in 2017: part of the World Craft Council, the proposal for the Island to be awarded with the title came from the roots, from the association itself. After the title, ACAB engaged in dialogue with Bornholm's Municipality in order to establish Maker's Island, a municipal committee to create value and build on the new title and identity of the Island. Maker's Island have been organizing in the past years events to display the arts and crafts of the island, such as the Craft Weeks, taking place each year at the beginning of the September and spread throughout the entire island. Additionally, every second year and in coincidence with the Craft Weeks, the island hosts the European Ceramic Context: a biannual exhibition and moment of dialogue around the ceramic sector in Europe.

A brief history of the ecosystem of Dals Långed and Fengersfors

Dals Långed and Fengersfors are two closely connected rural towns in the western part of Sweden. A key node in Dals Långed is Steneby, a creative and educational hub with two schools, Stenebyskolan and HDK-Valand Campus Steneby, where students are trained in material-based art and design (wood, metal, and textiles). Steneby also hosts a public library and an art gallery. Another key hub in Dals Långed is Studio Växt, initiated by former students, which offers a co-working space for creatives, fostering collaboration and innovation. A third hub is Långedsverken, a center for design-driven projects focused on wood, aiming to promote sustainable and circular furniture and interior design in Sweden.

Today, this area is an exception in the region of Dalsland because population is not decrease like in the other rural areas. Instead, the local development policies of this area is to make it possible to make a living from cultural and creative activities, even in a rural area. This policy, which is heavily sustained by regional funding and municipal support, is grounded in the several local hubs for arts and crafts, as described above, some of which are grassroot initiatives – Studio Växt and Not Quite – while others are institutional hubs – like the vocational school and the university campus. A very important actor in weaving together the policy and the different actors is an organization called Mötesplats Steneby which is primarily funded by the region and through project.

While Dalsland is today a depopulating rural region, it has historically been an important industrial place, also due to good water transportation, and a centre for crafts and handicraft. Harship has not spared the region and through hardship different crafts have emerged. During the famine of the 1860s, when hunger and mass emigration struck Dalsland, straw

craft emerged as an important cottage industry. Families turned to natural materials to create both decorative and practical objects, supplementing their income when farming could no longer secure their livelihoods. This heritage of resourcefulness would later form the basis for a stronger tradition of craft and design in the region.

In the early twentieth century, Sweden experienced a renewed interest in handicrafts, led by reformers such as Carl Malmsten at Nääs, near Gothenburg. His approach to education emphasized traditional knowledge, creativity, and hands-on learning, and attracted international recognition. Among those influenced by Malmsten was Erland Borglund, who studied at Nääs in the 1920s and carried these ideas back to Dals Långed. There he began offering woodworking courses for local youth, planting the seeds of what would later grow into an institution of national and international importance.

In the same period, Fengersfors was a hub for iron, pulp, and paper production. The iconic Fengersfors Bruk (mill) ceased its operations in 1978, marking the end of an industrial era. In 2003, a remarkable transformation took place, as the site was reimagined and repurposed to become a haven for the arts and crafts, as well as small businesses. This creative hub, named Not Quite, plays an important role in the local ecosystem as it hosts around 80 artists. The Not Quite compound features collective workshops, a garden, a bakery, a café, a bistro, a crafts shop, and galleries showcasing the artists' work.

In 1929, the Steneby Handicraft Association was founded as a gathering point for preserving and developing local skills. A few years later, in 1934, a school was established with Borglund as its first principal. The campus expanded in 1938 with the opening of a modernist dormitory and cafeteria, buildings that reflected the new architectural spirit of the time. During the Second World War, the school broadened its scope and offered courses in weaving, straw craft, carpentry, carving, turning, painting, bookbinding, metalwork, ceramics, tailoring, construction, and interior design. This broad curriculum ensured that students not only preserved traditional skills but also gained practical knowledge relevant to a rapidly changing world.

In the decades after the war, the school was incorporated into Sweden's national education system, which gave it stability and resources for growth. Throughout the 1960s new buildings were added, strengthening its role as a center of craft education. By 1991, the school had been reorganized as the Stenebyskolan Foundation, which focused on preparing students for professional and artistic careers. What had begun as a local initiative to keep craft traditions alive was by then an institution with broader ambitions, rooted in its regional identity but increasingly outward-looking. While the wider region of Dalsland faced economic and demographic challenges in the late twentieth century as well as a decline in industries, the arts and crafts education in Steneby/Dals Långed has turned to be a central pivot for a new crafts (and culture) based local development.

The beginning of the twenty-first century marked another step forward when Dals Långed became home to university-level education through a partnership with the University of Gothenburg. Students can now pursue degrees in *metal art, furniture design, and textiles*, and the campus has invested in state-of-the-art facilities such as a modern smithy,

digital woodworking tools, and expanded textile workshops. The programs attract people from all over the world, transforming a small community into a global meeting point for art, design, and craft. At the heart of this development remained the workshops and the emphasis on deep engagement with materials and processes, which made Steneby unique.

Today, the main materials in focus in local crafts are wood (also given the presence of a large forest), textile and metal. Stone work is also important given the closeness to the area of Bohuslän, which is rich in granite. While individual craftmakers might revive old techniques, for example in blacksmithing, most of the crafts are oriented to the renewal of crafts by finding new “uses” of craftmaking in the local community and to the experimentation of a craft-based social engagement for a sustainable and fair local economy. Here craft competences are used to a large extent for the building of common spaces and craftmaking itself is mostly organized through shared spaces.

With the strength of post-diploma and higher-education institutions, cultural initiatives played an important role in revitalizing local life. In Fengersfors, in 2002 a former paper mill was transformed into *Not Quite*, an artist collective and cultural center that has significantly grown both in terms of visitors and in terms of creators and entrepreneurs that are members of the collective. Exhibitions, studios, and community events breathed new life into the old industrial site and gave Fengersfors a reputation as a center of creativity. The collective has achieved a solid legitimacy in the artistic and cultural world so that it is nationally recognized in the cultural field as a destination and internationally known, especially for its participation in the Transeuropean Halles Network (THN). In 2022, Not Quite hosted the annual meeting of THN, consolidating its international recognition.

In Dals Långed itself, new initiatives such as *Studio Växt* created collaborative workspaces that linked students, professionals, and local residents. These projects demonstrated how education and culture could create positive effects that reached far beyond the classroom and out in the local community. Taking the advantage of relatively inexpensive real estate, craftmakers and artists have stayed after higher education, thus building a critical mass of competence that has transformed the towns of Dals Långed and Fengersfors and creating an attractive location for like-minded and like-interested to move to. Grassroots initiatives like Not Quite and Studio Växt have thus been essential to position this area on the map in the craft sector.

Apart from these grassroots initiatives and the school, a central actor for crafts in the area is an organization called *Mötesplats Steneby*, which is significantly financed by the region and has shifted organizational form over the years, from a project to a company. The mission of this organization is to make it possible to make a living by working with arts and crafts in this area. So, they actively initiate projects to make this possible and sustainable over time. One of the initiatives they have led is the renovation and reuse of an old industrial building called in Dals Långed to build a technologically up-to-date wood workshop which would allow the collaboration of the arts and crafts education, the wood industry and local craftmakers. This workshop is called *Open Wood* and has been the centre of industry-craft collaborative projects, partly funded through Interreg schemes. Currently, as a local site of

a controversy about what is the role of technologies in craft and how an open and sustainable governance is possible in a shared wood workshop, the HEPHAESTUS team has worked on a participatory process to unfold the controversy with the local community of craftmakers.

3.2. Urgencies and controversies

The second part of the results concern the discussion of the urgencies and controversies that we found in the different craft ecosystems of HEPHAESTUS through our methodology. These results are the product of the combination of all three pillars, with special significance of ethnographic and design methods which have allowed us to engage deeply with craftmakers, policy makers, educators and other local stakeholders' sensemaking of the cultural and socio-economic conditions of crafts locally. It has been important in the process to keep on the one hand a strong local sensitivity – in short, keep in mind the question of what are the concerns of the local craft ecosystems in light of HEPHAESTUS larger goals – and on the other hand a comparative eye across the ecosystems.

Thus, the results discussed in this section are divided in three main themes:

- I. Craft and cutting-edge technologies
- II. Craft and sustainability
- III. Craft and livelihood.

In each of these sections, we compare the different ecosystem, as an important step for mapping values of craft in the next section. By doing that, we capture the current urgencies of craft ecosystems, as voiced by the members of the ecosystem and especially in relation to two key focus of HEPHAESTUS, namely sustainability and digitisation, and to understand the degree of resistance or acceptance of digital and cutting-edge technologies and sustainability actions by the members of the ecosystems. For these purposes, ethnographic methods have been scientifically crucial and design methods have allowed us to make our results grounded and relevance in the site-specificities of each ecosystem.

3.2.1 Craft and cutting-edge technologies

The relationship between craft and technology has long been a subject of debate in design studies, craft research, anthropology and more recently also in organization studies. Craft is often positioned as the realm of handwork, tacit knowledge, and embodied skill, while technology is seen as mechanized, standardized, and disembodied (Adamson, 2019). This is also mirrored in much of the policy-makers' and practitioners' discourse. However, recent scholarship complicates this binary, emphasizing instead their entanglement. Richard Sennett (2008) highlights the “craftsman” as an archetype of skillful engagement with materials, stressing that craft is not opposed to technology but rather shaped through tools and techniques. Tim Ingold (2013) similarly argues that making is a process of correspondence with materials, where technology does not replace craft but mediates how humans relate to matter. Adamson (2013) sets the very constitution of craft as a social category in relation to industry and machinery and highlights the gray zones between craft

and industry, especially with regards to the use of machines in homes in the early industrialization period (see also Nilsson, 2015). David Pye’s distinction between the “workmanship of risk” and the “workmanship of certainty” (1968) further underlines how tools and technologies configure the balance between skill, control, and chance in making. Rather than drawing a clear line between craft and technology, Pye shows how craft practices shift along a continuum depending on the degree of reliance on tools and machinery. Technologies, whether simple tools or complex digital systems, shape both the possibilities and limitations of craft practice as well as the very definition of craft. As an illustration, the introduction of the potter’s wheel, the loom, and later industrial machinery continually redefined what counted as “handmade.”

Contemporary discussions often focus on digital fabrication and hybrid practices. Scholars such as Neil Gershenfeld (2005) and the makerspace literature highlight how CNC machines, 3D printing, and laser cutting are reimagined as craft tools, offering new affordances for experimentation and personalization and access to new social groups (Dioun et al., 2025). Yet, these technologies also provoke questions about authorship, authenticity, and the value of hand-made objects (Raviola et al., forthcoming; Harper-Davis & Raviola, forthcoming). Some argue that digital craft reconfigures skill: while manual dexterity may be less central, new competences in coding, designing, and operating digital systems become essential forms of craftsmanship.

At the same time, anthropological and feminist critiques caution against celebrating technology uncritically. Maria Puig de la Bellacasa (2017) and other STS and critical scholars highlight the ethics and politics of care embedded in craft practices (Vacchani et al., 2025), reminding us that technologies can both enable and erode these relational dimensions that are so important for the value of craft. Craft is not only about objects, but also about social practices, learning environments, and the values enacted through making. Recent work in organization studies has examined craft as a complex and multifaceted practice, understood not only as skilled material production but also as a mode of embodied, ethical, and relational engagement (Bell, Mangia, Taylor, & Toraldo, 2018; Bell & Vachhani, 2020). Craft objects have been analysed as meaningful artefacts (Holt & Yamauchi, 2019), as sites of resistance (Rippin & Vachhani, 2019), and as resources for imagining both past and future forms of work (Bell, Dacin, & Toraldo, 2021). Furthermore, scholars argue that craft functions as a political technology, shaping organizational practices and social relations (Black & Burisch, 2020). Digital technologies may foster global networks of makers, but they also risk reproducing exclusions, environmental costs, and labor inequalities.

Overall, the literature suggests that the dichotomy between craft and technology is less useful than an attention to how they co-constitute one another processually and in practice. As Gasparin and Neyland (2022) have argued, from the earliest Greek accounts, craft and technology have been closely intertwined, shaping how materiality and human affairs are organized (Beyes, Holt, & Pias, 2020). The very etymology of “technology” underscores this relation: derived from the Greek *tekhnologia*, it combines *tekhnē*—art or craft—with *logia*, the systematic study of an art. For the ancient Greeks, *tekhnē* referred to the art of bringing something into presence, whether a material object like a chair or a coat, an agricultural

yield, or even a divine word. Building on this literature that articulates a more complicated relationship between craft and technology than an opposition between the hand and the machine, HEPHAESTUS' researchers have teased out this relationship in the different ecosystems and, through a combination of methodologies, they have worked to stay with the trouble of this relationship, where craft emerges as a dynamic practice where tools, materials, and skills continually shift. Technologies are not external to craft but embedded within it, transforming both the aesthetics and ethics of making. This perspective opens space for examining hybrid forms of practice that value both tradition and innovation, hand and machine, care and efficiency.

The results of our studies in the four craft ecosystems present a variety of relationships between craft and technology, situated in the specific infrastructures of the ecosystem.

Venice and Bassano del Grappa

In Italy, the two ecosystems of Venice and Bassano del Grappa present different in terms of the organizational conditions of craft work inasmuch as in Venice many craftmakers are independent workers (apart from some exception in the heritage crafts like Murano glass), while in Bassano family businesses of ceramics production are very much alive and although new generations transform the size and nature of the business, the legacy of craft manufactures is still present.

In both ecosystems, the main controversy related to new technologies in craft concerns the fear that they may alter or even undermine the essence of artisanal work, which is traditionally grounded in manual skills and individual authorship. Techniques such as 3D printing or emerging tools like artificial intelligence are often perceived as incompatible with the notion of craft as a manual and embodied practice. This skepticism is reinforced by the fact that many artisanal processes are not easily automated and cannot seamlessly integrate technological inputs. For some artisans, this translates not only into *distrust* but also into a certain *disinterest* in adopting such tools. These attitudes are not uniform across the ecosystems: individuals with a background in industrial design, for instance, may be more open to experimentation, while others remain more cautious. Resistance is not limited to artisans. Since the market positioning of craft products often relies on their manual and traditional dimension, there is also uncertainty about how consumers would react to products partly produced with new technologies. While some see opportunities—especially if supported by specific branding strategies—others fear a loss of perceived authenticity.

At the same time, there are strong voices within the ecosystems advocating for the integration of technologies, pointing out the technical solutions and cost reductions they can offer. European cultural policies, such as those under Creative Europe, also encourage hybridisation between traditional craft and new technologies. Partial automation is indeed present since the 1960s in some sectors of the “Made in Italy” tradition, where craft intersects with industrial production. Other ecosystem actors, such as fablabs and makerspaces, promote a more gradual and experimental approach, often focusing on education and dissemination rather than immediate adoption.

Overall, it seems to us that the controversy remains very much open: the debate reflects broader societal tensions around technology, but in craft it is particularly pronounced because of the historical depth and cultural value associated with manual work in craft.

Bornholm

Within the craft panorama on Bornholm the relationship to technology, and in particular new technologies, is multifaceted and dependent on multiple factors, such as age, the kind of practice, and individual approaches to the practice. Taking into account the ceramic sector, for example, the relationship between the maker and the matter has a prominent role, under which the integration of new technologies in work processes, as might be the case of digital fabrication technologies, is looked at with suspect as a perceived risk is the decreasing knowledge of and contact with the matter. In other cases, the generation of the craftmaker plays a role in the consideration or decision to move towards new technologies: craftmakers from an older generation prefer to not engage with new technologies, as their language and style is based on their 'hands on' relationship with ceramic. On the other hand, some of the younger craftmakers, among which there are the students at the Royal Danish Academy, are more curious about new technologies. One of the considerations around the adoption of new technologies is about the use they [the craftmakers] can make of them: what I could observe as a common aspect of the ceramic sector is the possibility to use both *ad hoc* or *general* tools, in Sennett's words, so forks, old newspapers, or dismissed towels become means of experimentation and expressivity in the production of pottery.

Nevertheless, as several craftmakers showed a will to experiment and consider the adoption of new technologies in their practice, other considerations emerged, in particular about money and time, revealing how the access to new technology is controversial. If, on one side, the students of the Academy can experiment with the machines the school offers, the graduated craftmakers have to face more challenges to access them. What is concerning for them is that new technologies can be highly expensive, thus requiring a sensitive economic investment, but also requiring an investment in terms of time, necessary to learn how to use new technologies and then to integrate them in their work processes. While the Business Center Bornholm (BCB) organises courses for firms and entrepreneurs, regarding new technologies among a variegated offer, crafts does not represent the main or unique target of such courses, and craftmakers struggles to have access to different learning opportunities that can be complementary to their current knowledge. Another struggle is similarly the access to funding grants and opportunities to invest in new technologies: the options available for craftmakers are limited and usually devoted more to artistic research rather than experimentation in craft practices, if not misaligned with what craft practices involve: a craftmaker, for example, struggled to find a fund that could support the purchase of a new machine in order to experiment with recycled material, while other grants the craftmaker could find would support the construction of the machine itself rather than its purchase.

Other craft sectors on the island appears to be less connected to the use of new technologies, due to the nature of the craft, both in terms of tools and techniques as it might

be for glass blowing, textile work and woodwork. Glassblowing on Bornholm usually refers to or depart from techniques codified in the past, adopting tools that – despite the modernization of kilns and other machineries around – remained unchanged throughout centuries. Other sectors, such as textile and wood working, implies the use of different technological machines besides other techniques, where the necessity or will to adopt new technologies is more blurred or unclear. In particular, individual orientation and feelings about craft inform the decisions of each craftmakers to think about new technologies, even if they are looked at with curiosity.

Dals Långed

Within the Dals Långed ecosystem, the discourse and initiatives around new technologies in relation to craft play a prominent role, particularly with reference to key institutions and infrastructures in the area such as HDK-Valand Campus Steneby, Motesplats Steneby, and Open Wood. As an educational institution, HDK-Valand Campus Steneby has state-of-the-art workshop facilities equipped with advanced technologies aimed at supporting students' learning. As an organization focused on culture-led regional development, Motesplats Steneby seeks to support the integration of new technologies that could support their mission of making it possible for craftmakers to live off their craft and contribute to the sustainable development of the localities in which they live and work. One way in which Motesplats Steneby promotes the use and integration of advanced technologies in craft is through the Open Wood initiative, which aims to promote experimentation with new technologies for wood craft. Taken together, this puts cutting-edge technology as an important matter of concern in the ecosystem, including both the institutional drive towards it and the negative reactions or scepticism it elicits among some craftmakers.

Craftmakers in Dals Långed are generally open to new technologies. Some of them, for instance, combine traditional techniques with advanced digital techniques in their practice, and one could argue that there is a general attitude of experimentation that permeates the craft community in the ecosystem. Indeed, as an atypical rural area that receives many international students who come to receive higher education and training in craft, Dals Långed has no specific craft profile that would be tied to a long tradition deeply rooted in the history of the place. Rather, Dals Långed is characterized by renewal and innovation of different currents of craft, which make it more open to the exploration of new technologies. At the same time, there is a good deal of scepticism around efforts to actively promote the adoption of new technologies. Craftmakers want a thoughtful engagement beyond technology for technology's sake to avoid becoming “a tool, a new idiot”, as one craftmaker put it critically. Indeed, some are wary of what they view as a misguided attempt to scale up and industrialize craft incarnated in initiatives such as Open Wood (more on this below).

Focus 1: Open Wood and new technologies

Within the Swedish ecosystem, the complex relationship between craft and technologies has manifested in our research through a site-specific controversy, related to *Open Wood*, a state-of-the-art experimental workshop for wood manufacturing in an abandoned industrial premise in Dals Långed, Sweden.

As described in the methodological section of this report (see section 2.3), Open Wood is a publicly funded initiative that aims to reinforce the innovation environment in Dals Långed/Fengersfors by providing a shared workshop space equipped with cutting-edge technologies for wood craft. Open Wood uses a membership model and offers a range of activities to its members, including residencies and workshops. The membership model aims at offsetting certain costs linked to operation and maintenance, but Open Wood is ultimately a public infrastructure that needs support from the state to be able to run. Indeed, although the intention of Mötesplats Steneby (the regionally-funded organization working for the cultural and economic development of the area) was to develop Open Wood as a long-term infrastructure open to all local craftmakers interested in new technologies, the reality of project-based financing has come with some uncertainties that have resulted in risks surrounding its long-term viability. Mötesplats Steneby is persistently looking for funds to ensure the continuity of Open Wood, which means that the project has gone through a number of reframings and transition periods between funding rounds over the years. As one interviewee observed, Open Wood is forced to constantly re-describe itself repeatedly to gain new funding.

Now the current membership model consists of two pricing levels which are thought for both commercial and non-commercial projects. The higher price level is for commercial work, i.e. work that involves a paying client who has commissioned the assignment. The lower price level is for work done for experimental purposes, i.e. non-commercial work whose entire point is exploratory, meaning that the member/craftmaker is simply seeking to learn and innovate around their craft by experimenting with the technologies that are made available in this space. Members can combine both types of work, but the distinction is maintained through hourly packages at each price level relative to the nature of the work being performed. By limiting commercial production to smaller scale projects (series manufacture is not allowed) and promoting experimentation with cutting-edge technologies, Open Wood seeks to stay consistent with their mission of contributing to an innovation environment.

However, our analysis reveals that the “openness” and “sharedness” that animate the Open Wood project constitute an arena of contestation among craftmakers working in the area. For instance, some craftmakers pointed out that Open Wood has good aspirations of becoming a place of connection and material experimentation, but the financial uncertainties surrounding its survival sometimes curtail its capacity to turn these aspirations into reality; instead, Open Wood tends to become what the financiers, and their application processes, aspire it to be. Our site-specific controversy analysis of Open Wood uncovered two deeply interrelated issues in relation to this aspirational gap: (1) access and (2) community.

When it comes to (1) access, Open Wood has not always had the membership model described above. We interviewed some craftmakers before this model was implemented. At the time (autumn 2023), Open Wood was only available for projects of a non-commercial nature, and its focus was exclusively on promoting experimental and exploratory work. This decision was tied to questions of publicness in relation to the source of funding behind Open Wood, namely public funds. Should private businesses benefit from a public infrastructure? At the same time, craftmakers in the area who tend to have patchwork careers and rely on

different sources of income to make a living, had some difficulties with this model. Given their livelihood situation, they had to put their focus on commercial work, and so they could not afford to do experimental work, which de facto disqualified them from accessing Open Wood and its cutting-edge technological equipment. Some craftmakers, then, felt excluded, and thought that the then-current model of Open Wood did not reflect the realities of working life as a craftmaker. This was viewed as a lost opportunity by craftmakers interested in new technologies, as this exploratory framing was a luxury they could not afford. This situation changed with the implementation of the current dual model that permits both commercial and non-commercial work in the workshop.

In the ethnographic interviews, the issue of access also emerged in relation to the “high tech” or “cutting-edge tech” framing of Open Wood. The technology-centred idea of innovation embedded in Open Wood was off-putting to some craftmakers who questioned this framing as too business or industry oriented, which ran against prevalent ideas of craft held by some of them and performed in contrasting institutional infrastructures such as Not Quite. From this perspective, Open Wood could be seen as a threat to hands-on craft because of its digital and advanced technology aims. Moreover, we found that Open Wood was sometimes perceived as expert led, rather than education led, which appeared to raise the threshold of knowledge needed to use the workshop space, again excluding members of the local craftmaker community. Similarly, some of the craftmakers interviewed during our fieldwork expressed that Open Wood had a strong focus on the furniture industry, which constrained the scope of work one was allowed to experiment with, making the space less inviting and accessible for artists or craftmakers willing to explore and push their practice but whose work did not fit this narrow furniture-industry framing.

When it comes to (2) community, the controversy analysis revealed conflicting views as to what role Open Wood played in this context. Some interviewees expressed that Open Wood did provide a sense of community as a shared space where craftspeople could meet and find opportunities to collaborate with industry. Some people involved in the Open Wood project also envisioned to turn it into an incubator that could help newly graduated students from HDK-Valand Campus Steneby to kick-start their professional practice upon entering the workforce after graduation, solidifying their connections to place and people. But this idea of the incubator in particular, though generally popular, generates conflicting postures at the level of funding and funders. The region would like HDK-Valand Campus Steneby (University of Gothenburg) to co-finance the incubator, but HDK-Valand points to the region, claiming that if they ever set up an incubator as an educational institution, it would have to be in Gothenburg, not Dals Långed, as the school’s main location. Amidst these conflicting ideas of what Open Wood should or could be, some interviewees observed that the workshop space often sits empty, despite efforts to make it a lively place for experimentation for the local craftmaker community. Another interviewee highlighted how Open Wood tends to cater to white men, failing to include other members of the community, which points to the often-clashing dynamics that have surrounded the initiative.

Focus 2: Algorithmic visualization and craft process

A second focus in discussing the controversy between craft and technologies concerns the explorations we conducted at the intersection between traditional ceramics methods and algorithmic technologies of tracking and visualizing movements. Together with craft researcher and ceramicist Theodore (Theo) Harper Davis, we explored a novel intersection of traditional ceramics and emerging digital technologies that addressed the question of the relationship between hands and codes and between the visible and the invisible in craft. If craft is a process beside the product, can we datafy it? What would it look like? What implications would it have to have travelling craft data? And what would this mean for the value of craft?

Building on Harper-Davis' (2022) prior work in hand-printing clay—a hybrid technique developed during his PhD research *A Hybrid Origin*, we reframed craft not merely as the production of objects, but as a process of embodied movement and temporal gesture. Harper-Davis's approach treats clay as a medium for drawing, where bodily motion, rhythm, and time leave visible traces in three-dimensional space, while still producing ceramic products. In his studio, Harper-Davis gestures were recorded using motion sensors that tracked position, direction, and rhythm of the hand gestures. We also filmed the craft process with a camera fixed on the ceiling of his studio. These raw data streams were processed with AI-based pattern recognition algorithms, which cleaned the patterns of movement and through an algorithmic design software produce a visualization of the hand movement.

Figure 18 – Equipment used for motion tracking ceramic movements.

This visualization revealed the whole movement, from which we distilled distinct “motion signatures” that reflected the nuanced dynamics of his making. The resulting datasets were visualized as abstract, processual images by programmer and artist Fredrik Garneij, illustrating how movements accumulate and evolve over time—an intimate portrait of the maker's actions. Selected sequences of these visualizations were further transformed into 3D-printed forms, creating tangible artifacts derived not from the clay objects themselves, but from the gestures that produced them. These forms were exhibited at the Röhsska Museum of Design and Craft in Gothenburg alongside animated motion visualizations, inviting audiences to engage with the invisible dimensions of craft.

Figure 19 – Algorithmic visualization of craft movement

Figure 20 – Selected signature movements (visualized on the white cubes) and 3D prints of the signature movements (hanging on the ceramic sculpture)

The experiment yielded several key insights. Some 3D-printed shapes echoed the flows and contours of Harper-Davis's original clay work, while others revealed previously unnoticed aspects of his gestures. This divergence underscores the partial visibility of traditional craft objects: much of the maker's skill, timing, and expressive intent remains hidden in the physical process. By datafying movement, the project highlights the potential for motion to be archived as craft knowledge, suggesting that craftspeople may possess unique "movement signatures" as significant as their technical expertise.

The HEPHAESTUS experiment also challenges conventional notions of what constitutes a craft outcome. By capturing and re-materializing gestures through digital means, it situates craft as a living, dynamic, and expressive process. This approach not only foregrounds the human body and temporal rhythm in making but also demonstrates how technology can expand the ways in which craft knowledge is documented, valued, and exhibited. As such, the project bridges traditional skill-based practices with AI and motion-tracking technologies, revealing new perspectives on gesture, material intelligence, and the evolving relationship between maker, medium, and audience.

Focus 3: FabLab and traditional crafts

In collaboration with WP2, we set out to investigate the question of how hands and code can coexist in making together with craftmakers from the Swedish ecosystem and in what ways they might interact and enrich one another. To explore these questions, we organized a series of craftmaker residencies at FabLab Venice, bringing together craft ambassadors, new technologies, and cross-country collaboration, taking advantage of the technological competences of the FabLab and of the curiosity and interest of the Swedish craftmakers.

The residencies were designed as a learning journey, enabling craftmakers to experiment with digital tools while reflecting on their own practice. Following a workshop at Stone Zone in Sweden in September 2024 with Sweden-based craft ambassadors and FabLab representatives, three craftmakers (Lukas Arons, Linnea Dalstrand, and Rob Curran) engaged in a two-week residency in Venice between 10 and 22 February. This residency built on a previous visit to FabLab during the HEPHAESTUS kickoff in May 2023, where the craftmakers had initial exposure to the space but limited hands-on experience with its facilities. This visit had also raised some explicit controversies about the authenticity of machine-driven craft, especially in cases of heritage craft, and thus organizing the residencies and a preceding and following workshop was a designerly way of engage with the controversy in a participatory manner. As part of our ethical standing in HEPHAESTUS, the participatory spirit of our controversy mapping increases the relevance of the scientific results for craft practitioners.

At FabLab Venice, the makers engaged with technologies including 3D scanning, 3D printing, and laser engraving. Despite having minimal prior experience with digital fabrication, the craftmakers approached the residency with curiosity and enthusiasm. After an introductory session to the facilities and opportunities, each participant defined a specific

area of exploration: Lukas investigated 3D printing in combination with casting to examine surfaces and skin-like textures; Rob engaged in an iterative process pairing natural branch forms with 3D-printed supports, exploring the dialogue between organic and artificial structures; and Linnea experimented with laser engraving on textiles alongside scanning, modelling, and resin 3D printing to explore natural, decaying forms as exhibition supports.

The craftmakers kept reflexive auto-ethnographic diaries during the residencies, which helped them keep track of the encounters with new technologies and their learnings. We then used the crafted results from the residencies in a public exhibition at the Röhsska Museum of Design and Craft in Gothenburg, in May 2025. The exhibition, which a collaboration with WP6 and was installed besides the art-based explorations of *Brave New World* (WP3), was called “Datafying craft, Crafting data” and included the residencies’ results as well as the experiments with AI-enabled motion tracking of craft with Theo Harper-Davis. At the end of the exhibition, all craftmakers involved in these technological experiments held a public seminar for local policy makers, educators, researchers and craftmakers in the possibilities of encounters between craft and technologies.

Overall, the residencies demonstrated that digital fabrication and algorithmic design can complement traditional craft rather than disrupt it and can offer new ways of seeing and relating to the material. Digital tools provided new avenues for experimentation, enabling the makers to traverse their research paths in alternative ways while still retaining the embodied, material sensibility central to their practice. The craftmakers’ way of approaching new technologies turned out to be grounded in a crafterly way of relating to the material. For instance, a sculptor approached 3D printing as a way to build molds, turn them around and reprint them in different ways to produce sculptural effects and explore the machine-produced imperfections. At the same time, the experience highlighted that certain digital processes require external support or technical guidance, emphasizing the importance of collaborative ecosystems that integrate craft expertise with technological know-how.

Drawing on the HEPHAESTUS framework (see D1.2 – Report for policymakers with strategies for sustainable craft ecosystem management and heritage preservation, page 22), the figure below aims to summarize and contrast how present and prominent are discourses and initiatives around cutting-edge technologies in each ecosystem, as a way to gauge to what extent this topic has become a matter of concern in each instance. The vertical axis represents a continuum between innovating and maintaining, meaning that certain ecosystems will tend to innovate in relation to new technologies whereas others will tend to maintain certain techniques and traditions. The horizontal axis depicts a continuum between tacitness and explicitness in the sense of how backgrounded or foregrounded the issue of new technologies is within each ecosystem. In other words, how much of a backstage or frontstage do discourses and initiatives around new tech occupy in each case? In the case of Dals Långed, for instance, the relation of craft and new technologies is very explicitly discussed and negotiated in relation to initiatives such as Open Wood, as described above, where the aim is to generate innovation. By contrast, in an ecosystem like Bassano, the discussion around new technology revolves around how to maintain and protect manual work from automation, despite an increasing and explicit push towards adopting new technologies by certain institutions, as described above.

Figure 24 – Comparing ecosystems: craft-cutting-edge tech controversy

3.2.2. Craft and issues of sustainability

Craft has increasingly been discussed in relation to sustainability, both in terms of environmental practices and broader socio-cultural resilience. This relationship is complex inasmuch as on the one hand craft is often portrayed as carrying the ability to make the world more sustainable, beautiful and cohesive both through heritage identity-making crafts and new forms of crafts (see the NEB principles; REF.), but on the other hand a lot of traditional heritage crafts are environmentally problematic. Blacksmithing and glassblowing are emblematic illustrations of this complexity.

One of the central arguments is for craft practices as sustainable is their reliance on forms of material engagement that resist overproduction, overconsumption and planned obsolescence. Some forms of craft in our ecosystems are particular inclined to bear this argument. For instance, the Scandinavian idea of *slöjd* promotes the possibility of resilience through making with what is at hand and repairing continuously (Hansson & von Busch, 2023). Kate Fletcher and Mathilda Tham (2019) have also emphasized how craft foregrounds durability, repair, and care in ways that challenge fast-paced, resource-intensive production systems. Hand-making and small-scale production not only reduce environmental impact but also foster deeper relationships between makers, users, and objects, extending their lifespans. This echoes Tim Ingold's (2013) argument that craft involves a responsiveness to materials and environments, a way of "corresponding" with the world that is inherently ecological.

Besides the environmental elements of sustainability, we can also understand it socially and culturally. As HEPHAESTUS foregrounds by focusing on the social, economic and cultural conditions of possibility for crafts – traditional and in renewal, craft practices often sustain local economies, skills, and traditions that might otherwise be lost under globalized production models. Adamson (2013) has highlighted how craft can serve as a repository of cultural heritage, maintaining knowledge across generations while adapting to contemporary contexts. This continuity ensures not only the preservation of traditions but also the resilience of communities in the face of economic and ecological disruptions.

At the same time, the literature acknowledges tensions. Craft is not automatically sustainable; it can rely on scarce or extractive materials, and artisanal production may become commodified in ways that primarily serve luxury markets. Critics caution against romanticizing craft, pointing to issues of labor inequality, appropriation, or the environmental costs of certain practices (Corvellec, Stowell, & Johansson, 2022). Feminist and postcolonial perspectives emphasize that sustainability must be understood alongside justice, care, and inclusivity (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017).

Recent work also explores the role of craft in sustainable innovation. Makerspaces, repair cafés, and DIY cultures merge traditional craft skills with contemporary practices of sharing, recycling, and open-source design. These hybrid spaces illustrate how craft knowledge contributes to circular economy models by extending product lifecycles and revaluing waste

materials (Rosner & Ames, 2014; Twigger Holroyd, 2017). They also demonstrate how infrastructures of repair and upcycling help reframe sustainability as a cultural and political project, not merely a technical one (Kuijjer & de Jong, 2012; Rosner, Ikemiya, & Regan, 2015). Such practices show that sustainability is deeply connected to the values, relations, and forms of care embedded in making.

The literature, thus, positions craft as both a material and social practice that can contribute to sustainability by fostering durability, care, and community resilience. Rather than offering a nostalgic alternative to modern production, craft practices invite a reconsideration of how making, using, and valuing things might align with more sustainable ways of living in different ways in different ecosystems.

Venice and Bassano del Grappa

Compared to the other domains, controversies around sustainability are less acute in the two Italian ecosystems, since craft—due to its small-scale and often localised production—has historically and currently been seen as a relatively sustainable mode of production. The limited scale of production has allowed many artisans to align with principles of sustainability and to market their products as environmentally friendly without having to radically change their business models. Some artisans, especially in Venice, actively highlight this aspect in their branding, while others go further and experiment with innovative sustainable materials, such as cork or mycelium-based leather alternatives.

Nonetheless, tensions do emerge. For example, traditional gondola makers in Venice have contested EU regulations on the use of certain materials, which forced them to adopt new adhesives that are more expensive and alter their established techniques. Nonetheless, it is not always the case; in glass and ceramics, by contrast, the transition away from toxic materials such as lead or arsenic has been largely welcomed, especially by younger generations who witnessed the health impacts on their older relatives. Here, environmental and occupational health issues may overlap, creating a smoother path for change, even if only the decline of industrial ceramic production has allowed a decrease in the High levels of particular matter in the Nove area.

Another minor but recurring tension concerns access to waste and by-products: current EU and national regulations often make it difficult for artisans to reuse their own scraps or access residual materials from other industries, limiting experimentation with circular economy models.

Bornholm

Craftmakers on Bornholm prioritize sustainability in their practice, also in light of the overall policy of circularity on the island. Bornholm in fact strives to become a fully circular island by 2030 and craftmakers have taken, through the triggering effect of HEPHAESTUS and its living lab, a central role in this transition. They indeed agree on a more sustainable aspect in their works, and at the same time are more sensitive to what in their practices can be improved on a sustainability ground. Ceramicists are acutely aware how kilns and other

machines consume resources, and the disposal of waste is also a thoughtful topic. In ceramic, almost every craftmaker owns particular sink-filters to collect the clay that is washed off hands, tools, and defected pieces. The use of materials and their disposal are elements upon which they reflect, and several craftmakers are exploring and experimenting with different recycled materials. Nevertheless, across every craft sector the material quality of waste and its provenance, the previous use of it, and the acknowledgement of its original composition and its production processes are determinant aspects that inform the possibility to re-use a specific material to produce new objects to be commercialized. To study and conduct analysis, or to verify whether the use of a material is possible or not, require often expensive procedures and time.

While craftmakers experiment and try to consider environmental sustainability in their practice, the necessity to balance between economic and aesthetic sustainability similarly emerges. Indeed, while the use of recycled material can be an opportunity for them, on the other there might be the lack of time and resources to devote more effort into experiments rather than on a more controllable product. In particular, the material knowledge of the materials and components used in craft, perfected in years, is at the basis of the production of the craftmakers. Thus, efforts in terms of environmental sustainability – optimizing resources, using waste, sharing with other craftmakers – are spent as much as it is possible to keep a balance with the economic sustainability of craft work. The orientation towards more sustainable practice and materials at the same time takes into account the aesthetic quality of craft work, as a priority is still doing beautiful things, while the results of experiment with specific materials might not produce high standard results.

Dals Långed

Craftmakers in Dals Långed have a very strong connection to sustainability issues in relation to their practice. In fact, some craftmakers who had previous careers in other trades or fields (such as design) turned to craft precisely as a way to engage with more sustainable ways of working with making/producing. Craft is seen as an alternative way of organizing production (opposed to industrial production) that bestows makers with greater agency to determine the environmental impact of their work. For instance, one interviewee recounted how craft became a way for her to exert more control over her creative work by being involved in the full production cycle, from harvesting her own materials to life after use when the crafted object may be reused, recycled, repurposed, or simply end up being soil again. This overview and influence on the whole cycle is deeply valued by craftmakers in Dals Långed.

Similarly, other craftmakers pointed to how craft enables one to take responsibility for raw materials and production processes in a way in which, say, design cannot. For design is limited by an industrial division of labour that separates conception from production, involving different professionals along the process who may override decisions made in the conception phase. Designers, in this sense, are seen as having less agency in comparison to craft, not only in relation to production processes but also in terms of production volumes. One craftmaker likened the sustainability of craft to “being a good ambassador for

everything” and described it as “a love for the forest to the finished product”. As a key infrastructure in the ecosystem, Open Wood itself is premised on this idea around sustainable production and circularity, as it spans the whole value chain of the wood industry from the actual forest producer/owner to the recycling companies.

Focus: Bornholm and the Crushing Machine

As a focus on craft and sustainability and the possibility to work on this complex relationship in a propositve way, we will now discuss the experimental work of an innovative ceramicist on Bornholm. This experimental work allows us also to intersect the relationship between craft and sustainability with technology offering new possibilities of using new machines to make craft more sustainable.

Christina Schou is an experienced and internationally-renown ceramicist from the Bornholm. Our research has focused on her ceramicist’s technique as well as on her organizational innovation. The research focused on the used-ceramics crushing machine acquired by Schou and its role in renewing and expanding her craftwork and her business model towards sustainability through circularity. The crushing machine is a key resource that enables Christina to transform waste ceramic materials into glazes. This crushing machine allows her to expand her business model and sustain her value. By potentially becoming a supplier of these glazes under her second brand, *Experimental Glazes*, she opens a new revenue stream, which can provide her with financial stability and also expands her reach. However, this shift also presents new challenges associated with the transition to a supplier role.

The crushing machine acquisition helped Christina in expanding her existing portfolio of activities – such as teaching at the Royal Danish Academy, participating in the Chimney Project, attending Bornholm Craft Week events, and selling sculptures through galleries – into new directions. Following the acquisition, her capabilities of developing new crafts and new areas for craft competencies are shown to have grown, allowing her the opportunity of opening an online store (*Experimental Glazes*) for selling her own waste-based glazes and hosting workshops. Through this expansion, there has been also potential for collaboration with larger industry partners seeking more sustainable and/or custom glaze solutions. Importantly, the crushing machine has not only improved sustainability and opened the possibility for a sustainable business model, but it has also enhanced the craftmaker’s knowledge of glaze production and opened new avenues for creative exploration, from unique sculptures to experimental material combinations, all the way to coming up with original waste-based recipes of glazes and building an open source of knowledge in the form of a public library of recipes.

Figure 25 – Ceramic crushing machine on Bornholm.

Comparing the ecosystems – craft and sustainability

Drawing on the HEPHAESTUS framework (see D1.2 – Report for policymakers with strategies for sustainable craft ecosystem management and heritage preservation, page 22), the figure below aims to summarize and contrast how present and prominent are discourses and initiatives around sustainability in each ecosystem, as a way to gauge to what extent this topic has become a matter of concern in each instance. The vertical axis represents a continuum between innovating and maintaining, meaning that certain ecosystems will tend to seek how to innovate in relation to sustainability, whereas others will tend to seek to maintain certain techniques and traditions above sustainability concerns. The horizontal axis depicts a continuum between tacitness and explicitness in the sense of how backgrounded or foregrounded the issue of sustainability is within each ecosystem. In other words, how much of a backstage or frontstage do discourses and initiatives around sustainability occupy in each case? For instance, in the case of Bornholm, sustainability is a central concern explicitly tied to the island's ambition to become fully circular and go zero waste in the near future, for which they have enlisted craft in their innovation efforts. By contrast, in an ecosystem like Bassano, discussions and initiatives around sustainability tend to be more low-key.

Figure 26 – Comparing ecosystems: craft-sustainability controversy

3.2.3. Craft and making a living/livelihood

In recent years, the resurgence of craft in contemporary society has spawned a growing interest in the concept and practice of craft in sociological studies of occupation (Bell et al., 2018; Kroezen et al., 2021). This literature is particularly relevant here because one of the key urgencies that HEPHAESTUS researchers found in the different craft ecosystems concerns the value of craftwork and the struggles of how craftmakers can sustain their livelihood in contemporary capitalism.

Organizational research on craft has shown how the introduction and elevation of craftwork in particular sectors has effected profound changes not only in production processes, but in the configuration of sectors in their entirety, such as beer brewing (Kroezen & Heugens, 2019) or service work in supermarkets (Endrissat et al., 2015). Craft has been conceptualized as an alternative approach to industrialized work and organization that emphasizes human engagement in making, often symbolized by “the hand”, and that is set in opposition to more conventional approaches predicated on rationalization and mechanization of tasks (Kroezen et al., 2021). As such, craft has re-entered the

stage of organizational and economic life as an emergent form of post-industrial work that promises to better respond to the societal and environmental challenges of our epoch, serving as a more ethical model for innovation and creativity (Schaefer & Hallonsten, 2023) and a source for more inclusive imaginaries of production and consumption (Bell et al., 2021).

In an attempt to parse contemporary craft work, different categorizations have been advanced in the literature. Kroezen et al (2021) draw a distinction between industrialized craft and other forms of creative and pure crafts. “Neo-craft” is another category that has been deployed to describe contemporary craft work characterized by an aura of ‘coolness’ (Gandini and Gerosa, 2023). Neo-craft work is conceptualized as a response to the alienation of industrial work and the search for authenticity and status tied to ‘hipster’ culture (Gandini and Gerosa, 2023)—a form of work that has become appealing to those who have declined to follow more traditional pathways to education and work life (Ocejo, 2017). Yet another category that has been used is that of craftivism (Greer, 2014), meaning the practices of resistance involved in craft work. Indeed, design and craft scholars have assigned craft a significant ability to create spaces of resistance to the dominant industrialized capitalism, yet gentle ones insofar as they do not appear as a radical rupture but entail more of a marginal coexistence.

While craft carries often the connotation of offering alternatives to unsustainable capitalist organizing, the connection between ideas of craft and ways in which craftmakers organize their working life is overlooked. The conditions of employment and economic sustainability of craft work are indeed varying in different contexts and places. Some crafts are organized in small factories and large workshops employing several artisans, while others blur boundaries between amateurs and professionals and unfold in independent freelance work, shared workshops and entrepreneurial initiatives. In this paper, we are particularly interested in the latter mode of organizing craft that involves independent workers in forms of pure and creative craft (Kroezen et al., 2021), often operating through their own individual company and navigating different ways of making a living with, through, around and besides craft and we are interested in the ways in which their ideas of craft and the ways in which they organize their working life are recursively performative.

Throughout the different ecosystems in focus in HEPHAESTUS, we found that many of these craft workers share their time across many occupations and workplaces in different ways over the seasons of the year. This state of affairs is not unique in the creative industries, where precarious work is the norm (Morgan & Nelligan, 2018). Scholars have also used the notion of hyperemployment (Quaranta & Jansa, 2020) and entreprecariat (Lorusso, 2020) to denote the ways in which the independent creative work is organized today, from project to project and across many projects at the same time. Craft is not an exception.

In the remaining of this section, we present how specific controversies around craft and livelihood manifest themselves in the different ecosystems.

Venice and Bassano del Grappa

A central way in which the controversy about livelihood unfolds in the Italian ecosystems is the distinction between amateur and professional practice. In certain crafts—such as ceramics, where the barrier to entry is relatively low—it is possible for hobbyists to produce items that directly compete with professional artisans on the same markets, such as local fairs. This creates tensions, especially when informal or untaxed activities allow hobbyists to sell at lower prices. In crafts like glassmaking, where infrastructure and expertise requirements are higher, the boundary between amateur and professional practice is clearer and the controversy less pronounced.

A second, more structural controversy concerns the difficulty of sustaining a livelihood through craft. Unless operating in luxury segments, which yet remain difficult to access and unstable in terms of margins, many artisans struggle to rely exclusively on their craft income. As a result, they often combine multiple jobs, some unrelated to creative work, in order to maintain their practice. This feeds into a broader criticism by artisans and professional associations, particularly in Italy, that the sector—despite its cultural and symbolic importance—is not adequately supported by public policies. Calls range from direct funding schemes to the simplification of bureaucratic procedures, which are often seen as excessively burdensome for small-scale craft enterprises.

Bornholm

The main controversy or tension mentioned directly by the craftmakers involved in the Bornholm's craft sector is usually of economic nature. "I would need more money", I often heard. Nevertheless, behind that request tensions arise in relation to areas as technology, livelihood and sustainability, such as barriers to access to grants or other funding opportunities for craft, as current possibilities are often more oriented towards art rather than craft per se; feelings of misunderstanding or incomprehension between craftmakers and municipality; the presence of internal and external pressures; difficulties in accessing other learning opportunities.

Rather than professional craft and hobbyism, some tensions in terms of livelihood emerged regarding the relationship between craft and other actors within the ecosystem. Indeed, many craftmakers got closer to craft in the mode of a hobby, as they looked for a way to express themselves, turning it, only in a second moment, in an economic activity. To sustain their craft, some craftmakers – in particular ceramists – organise workshops for tourists and amateurs who are interested in it. More tense is the relationship with the municipality and to the Maker's Island committee. The committee is formed by municipality's officials and by some craftmakers, and, despite the collaboration, a struggle to communicate and to find a mutual understanding emerged. For example, craftmakers felt they are not taken into account enough in meetings – as last minute communication and a lack of respect of their time – and in the organization of events, such as the Craft Weeks. Furthermore, while efforts and resources are spent to create value out of the island's brand, some craftmakers felt they are not represented properly for what they would need.

Another tension that emerged from conversations and interviews, is the relevance of external pressures and power imbalances, as sometimes a lack of independence

might arise. In particular, some long term strategies are at risk as the capacity to move along the ‘World Craft Region brand’ is jeopardized by shifts in internal and external political agendas. A case is Maker’s Island, whom survival have been at risk throughout the present year: with the elections on the island and a change in the administration, a different political agenda could have marked the end of Maker’s Island funding after the 2025 Craft Weeks. Although Maker’s Island has been granted more funds and time for the following years, the risk of changes and the uncertainty remain a recurrent threat. Another case is the Royal Danish Academy in Bornholm. On one hand it constitute an attractor for students from around the world – who might decide to remain on Bornholm after the bachelor – and it contributes to reinforce the role of craft on the island. On the other hand, decisions around the programmes and the offering cannot be made independently from the main institution in Copenhagen, which in turn has decisional capacity and is as well informed by shifts and changes in Danish Government’s guidelines in terms of educational offers and programmes. The influence of these kind of pressures constitute a tension for the actors on Bornholm that operate around craft.

As mentioned above, another particular tension is the struggle for the craftmakers to live only by the work of their hands, as often they do more than one job. The tension appears to concern more the younger generations of craftmakers, as older generations described the multiple jobs as natural for a part of their careers. On the other hand, younger generations prefer to work on their craft, trying to orient additional occupations toward the same sector (e.g. organizing workshops). Some craftmakers managed to have a job at the Academy, while others found parallel occupations in other sectors. Similar to the approach to technology, the matter of multiple occupations as controversy depends on the inclination and preferences of the individual craftmakers. Indeed, other jobs can be a burden for some craftmakers, for others another occupation might concern other objects of interest in their life (e.g. jobs dedicated to youth care or the community) or can be directly functional to craftwork as a moment of pause and reflection around the profession or projects the individual craftmaker carries on.

Dals Långed

In Dals Långed, craftmakers are often confronted with livelihood struggles, which is one of the most important urgencies or tensions that emerge from the empirical material. Craftmakers combine their craft practice with other jobs in order to make a living. These are bread-and-butter jobs (in Swedish *brödföda*), seen as more stable and secure, because living on their primary practice (professional craft making) is not enough to sustain themselves. Most people also apply for external funding such as scholarships, project funding, etc. One craftmaker described this as a “patchwork” career which is very common among people working with craft in this rural area. It may include teaching, service jobs, or working at the local bakery, as many of our interviewees noted.

Combining different jobs is not just for the sake of economic survival nor is it always a burden. Rather, our interviewees also admitted that they like to do different things. We use here the metaphor of juggling to illustrate the craft makers’ practice of combining many jobs.

The idea of juggling, i.e. throwing several objects in the air, catching them and keeping them moving, is particularly suitable here as the craft makers seem to assign different functions to different jobs and to try to keep their working life moving while the jobs that they juggle might change. Even if other activities are taking time from craft practice, the variety of jobs (the juggling movement) is unimaginable to renounce to. For instance, one interviewee mentioned that they could not see themselves not working as a teacher at the school, because it enriched her relational life and fed her own craft practice. In this sense, some jobs are good to have not only to earn money, but also as an opportunity to meet different people and have a varied and rich work life.

Not only the jobs outside craft practices produce different spheres of labour that the craft makers juggle with, but the very craft practice generates different labours. For example, to keep costs down, the studios and workshops are often shared with many others, which demands acts of negotiation, sometimes even breakouts because of conflicts. Being part of a collective also means one is spending a lot of time on unpaid labour, for the shared common good. As jugglers, our craft makers catch and throw the balls again and again quickly, one at a time, to always keep at least one ball in the air.

Comparing the ecosystems – craft and livelihood

Drawing on the HEPHAESTUS framework (see D1.2 – Report for policymakers with strategies for sustainable craft ecosystem management and heritage preservation, page 22), the figure below aims to summarize and contrast how present and prominent are discourses, initiatives and struggles around livelihood in each ecosystem, as a way to gauge to what extent this topic has become a matter of concern in each instance. The vertical axis represents a continuum between innovating and maintaining, meaning that certain ecosystems will tend to innovate how to make a living, whereas others will tend to seek to maintain a certain model that has worked in the past. The horizontal axis depicts a continuum between tacitness and explicitness in the sense of how backgrounded or foregrounded the issue of livelihood is within each ecosystem. In other words, how much of a backstage or frontstage do discourses and initiatives around livelihood occupy in each case? For instance, in the case of Bornholm, livelihood struggles are a recurrent issue, which has drawn explicit attention, but the discussions have tended to revolve around how to maintain a model based on selling craft. By contrast, in an ecosystem like Dals Långed, livelihood struggles are also explicitly acknowledged as acute, but the discourses and initiatives in the ecosystem revolve around innovating and creating new ways to make a living under the frame of a culture-led regional development as promoted by Motesplats Steneby.

Figure 27 – Comparing ecosystems: craft-livelihood controversy

3.3. Mapping values of craft in different ecosystems

In line with Gasparin and Quinn (2021), HEPHAESTUS adopts an ecosystem perspective to craft, through which we reveal how the contributions of craftsmanship extends beyond the cultural and economic domains to embrace the very social fabric of a place. Craft work is inherently multi-value, generating social, economic, cultural, and environmental outcomes. Social values arise from the benefits that culture and creativity provides to communities, but specifically craft carries the value of heritage, which is central to the cultural identity of a place, and the value of communities of care and repair. Literature on creative industries in developed countries suggests that culture and creativity support urban regeneration (Evans & Shaw, 2004), foster social inclusion (Belfiore, 2004), and deliver broader social benefits (Luckman & Thomas, 2023). While policy and scholarship increasingly recognize the multiplicity of craft values, there is still a lack of a fine-grained analysis and representation of these values, including struggles and controversies of contemporary craft, beyond the neoliberal orientation of the construct of cultural and creative industries.

Beside and, most importantly, beyond the economic valorization of craft, we want to lift through our research the social values of craft through their cultural heritage which is carried by craft work even in processes of innovating craft. Our research shows how craft work contribute to inclusion and social cohesion, especially in places where the role of craft is

prioritized as central in policies of sustainability and regional development. Cultural values represent the beliefs, traditions, heritage, and ethical principles that guide communities. These values foster sustainable societies and help establish shared identities, reinforcing the broader contribution of craft and creativity to collective well-being.

Based on the three urgencies that we identified in the ecosystems of HEPHAESTUS, we have thus mapped their value system in a visualization that renders the different cultures of craft in the different places. While this is an important result in its substantial contribution to understand the cultural differences of contemporary craft, it is important for our research that this mapping method leaves beyond the very specificities of our research. By acknowledging the varieties of craft controversies and analysing them in depth in their embeddedness in the local social, economic, cultural and historical fabric, this portrays a more nuanced understanding of craft, in line with our many Europes. This is a line of research that goes through HEPHAESTUS as a whole and that is reflected also in other work packages and initiatives. Emblematic here is the work performed in Work Package 3 and 6 on the Atmospheres of Craft and the different speculations around craft, presented and discussed differently in different ecosystems and with different publics.

For each ecosystem, a visualization of their value system based on the research is provided below. The three main themes encompassing the urgencies and controversies (cutting-edge technology, sustainability, and livelihood) are represented in each visualization. The extent to which these themes are present as matters of more or less importance or concern in each ecosystem is visually represented by how close the point of convergence is to the end of the line at each instance (the further from the center and closer to the end of the line, the more prominent or important the matter of concern is). This is further complemented by accentuating the intensity of these values and concerns in a color-coded manner whereby red represents the highest intensity and yellow the lowest (which corresponds to the tacitness/explicitness continuum described previously).

Indeed, these figures visually summarize in a different manner the insights provided in the preceding sections (i.e. section 3.2.1, section 3.2.2, and section 3.2.3) including the figures comparing each ecosystem presented at the end of each of these sections. The figures below, however, integrate the three themes and are divided by ecosystem, which provides another way of appreciating and comparing the findings. For instance, Dals Långed is consistently in tension and experiences urgencies/controversies in relation to all three themes. Whereas in ecosystems like Venice and Bassano certain matters of concern tend to take prevalence over others in each case. In this way, these visualizations provide a glimpse of how certain values are enacted in each ecosystem relative to the conditions and challenges found in each case.

Figures 28-31: Craft value maps of each ecosystem along the three identified controversies

4. Conclusions

The HEPHAESTUS mapping of the craft ecosystems offers an innovative, multidisciplinary and participatory methodology and reveals that while craft continues to play a vital role in sustaining local identities, cultures and economies, it faces multiple vulnerabilities that align closely with UNESCO’s classification of risks to intangible cultural heritage. Demographic change and weakened transmission threaten the continuity of knowledge in places like Bornholm, while economic pressures and cultural globalisation are particularly visible in

Venice and Bassano del Grappa, where dependence on tourism reshapes traditional practices. In Sweden, hesitations and tensions around digitisation reflect both negative attitudes and the disruptive potential of new products and techniques. To different extents, but across all ecosystems, environmental degradation and changing material ecologies add an additional layer of urgency to questions of sustainability.

These risks highlight not only the fragility of craft heritage but also its potential as a living resource. By tracing the historical continuities and contemporary controversies that shape each ecosystem, our research demonstrates that heritage cannot be treated as a static legacy, but as a dynamic process constantly negotiated among makers, institutions, markets, and publics. The UNESCO risk categories provide a useful framework for situating local vulnerabilities within a broader international perspective. Our ethnographic and designed methodology complements this framework of risk, by further revealing how they are entangled with contemporary debates on sustainability and digitisation.

For Europe, the preservation and renewal of craft heritage is both a cultural and an economic concern. It is a cultural concern because craft is a form of cultural heritage deeply embedded in social practices, identities, and territorial histories. The continuities we traced—through materials, skills, and community ties—reveal how crafts sustain cultural memory. It is an economic concern inasmuch as craft is tied to the resilience of regional economies, the cultivation of sustainable practices, and the safeguarding of collective identity. The HEPHAESTUS project shows that by documenting urgencies, values, and controversies in a comparative and participatory way, it is possible to both understand what is at stake for craft today and to open up pathways for its future. Craft heritage thus emerges not only as something to protect from loss, but as a foundation for innovation, collaboration, and cultural sustainability across Europe.

A brief note on the fifth ecosystem

In the research planning phase, the HEPHAESTUS project design envisaged the examination of five craft ecosystems. Due to logistical constraints, one ecosystem – the Faroe Islands – could not be fully integrated within the timeframe of this report. The research team decided to focus on four ecosystems—Dals Långed, Bornholm, Venice, and Bassano del Grappa—ensuring that the comparative analysis remains robust, as these four contexts represent diverse geographical, cultural, and socio-economic conditions.

This adjustment has allowed the team to deepen the empirical and analytical work in each case, enhancing the richness and quality of the findings presented. Work related to the Faroe Islands ecosystem may still be pursued in the remaining months of the project, potentially allowing its integration in follow-up analyses and dissemination activities. This approach balances methodological rigor with practical constraints, while keeping open the possibility of extending the comparative framework in the near future.

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Appendix 1 – Interview Guide

This interview guide is conceived as a flexible and open tool to prepare the researchers for ethnographic interviews with members of the field, including craftmakers, policy makers, local organizations and other stakeholders. Each subject area is a suggestion about possible questions to ask, but since these interviews are conducted in the ethnographic spirit it is important to establish a relation in the conversation and to follow-up from the participants' narratives.

This interview guide is mainly written for interviews with the craftmakers, but it is to be adapted for other interviews by asking about craft work and policies as well as expanding questions about the ecosystem and the role of specific stakeholders in the ecosystem.

WARM UP

Can you describe your background (geographic, education briefly)?

Can you tell me the story of your professional career and your company?

How would you define yourself (occupation-wise)

CRAFT

What kind of craft you work today with? (issues, materials, tools etc.)

Interview on site: Tell me about your working space

Which tools do you use? How have they changed over time?

Where do your materials come from? Have they changed over time?

Where do you sell your crafts? / who pays for your crafts?

How does a year of work look like?

How does a working day look like for you?

(Here it is possible to take up security at work, as a possible issue)

How has your work changed over time?

ECOSYSTEM - PLACE

How would you describe your area of work? (Why do you work here?)

How are your relations with other craftmakers? (who is a colleague and which relations are in place?) and with other actors in the ecosystem?

Would you have been able to find these materias/relations/knowledges elsewhere? (This question hints at the sense of place)

ECONOMY

Do you have other jobs?

How do you make a living?

How do you think about the relations between different jobs you do?

TECH

Do you use digital technologies? Which ones? How?

How do you learn about new technologies?

Do you see potential for craft? Or not?

FUTURE

What would you suggest to a person that wants to do your job?

What do you feel/think you are missing knowing? What would you like to know how to do?

What would make your work easier?

Appendix 2 – Coding Protocol

Instructions on the coding:

- The codes are indeed descriptive and they make sense once we have many interviews to compare.
- It is necessary to make more specific subcodes (in NVivo child codes) under each of them;
- Codes can be then taken separately and analyzed theoretically according to each researcher's interest.
- It is very important to write memos and/or annotations in order to keep track of our analytical thinking during the coding and the ideas we get. (This dual process of coding and memoing is the basic skeleton of grounded theory – for future reference).

Middle range codes:

- Life stories of craft people
This code is about how craft people tell the story of their life, background, travels, what has informed them, etc. We have a question at the beginning of the interview about their background, but it can also come in other answers.
- Materials of craft
This code contains the descriptions of the materials used and how they are used, where they come from, how they are experimented with, etc.
- Making of craft:
Tools, techniques of making, different processes for craft/art
- Selling craft/making craft public
This code is about the processes by which craft reaches or construct publics, it could be the markets of different kinds, or cultural institutions for exhibitions or festivals or other activities. Also social media activities go here.
- Administrating craft
This code is thought for processes of approaching craft in public bureaucracies, for writing policies, promoting craft, counting craftmakers etc.
- Labels of craft work/ers:
These are the ways in which craft work/ers are referred to or refer to themselves, like craftmakers, artists, artisans, sellers, etc.
- Making a living:

This code captures the different activities available to or made by craftmakers to make a living and/or make money and/or develop a business and how they relate to each other

- Relationships of craft work:
These are all the relations in which craft is happening and around the craft workers that are considered relevant for craft, for example colleagues, friends, family, but also nature, raw materials, tools. Capturing the network (in human/social terms) the theme of network
- Place of craft:
This code is about connotations about the places which we have chosen as our ecosystems. Also the relevance of the specific town/neighborhood (i.e. 9 for pottery, Murano for glass). The role of tourism in a given place might also go here.
- Spaces of craft:
These are the spatial descriptions and references of the locations/sites in which craft work happens in these ecosystems, like workshops, old factories, studios, etc.
- Skills of craft:
These describe what the craft workers can do, how they train formally and informally and what they feel they need to know more. Also what they want to learn better and what they would like to outsource
- Futures of craft:
This code is about how craft people talk and imagine the futures of craft.
- Past of craft:
This code is about how craft people talk about the past, tradition of craft, nostalgia or not.
- Ideas of craft:
This code aims at collecting how explicit idea of Craft are formulated by our interviewees. They are a sort of theories-in-action/use of craft, referring to general understanding of what craft produces at societal level. For example, political ideas of craft (craft against capitalism) or therapeutic ideas of craft (craft for wellbeing), or others.
- Critical events:
This code is about how bigger societal events are talked about by our interviewees in relation to craft or to their personal life story, for example the financial crisis, the pandemic, the climate crisis, etc.

